

Empa

Materials Science and Technology

SMARTCARB 2

Use of satellite measurements of auxiliary reactive trace gases for fossil fuel carbon dioxide emission estimation (Phase 2)

**Final report of ESA study contract n°4000119599/16/NL/FF/mg
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Executive summary and recommendations

This extension of the SMARTCARB project (referred to as SMARTCARB-2 in the following) had two main elements: (i) an extended and deeper analysis of the COSMO-GHG atmospheric transport simulations and synthetic satellite observations of CO₂ and NO₂ generated in SMARTCARB-1, and (ii) an analysis of the realism of the simulations of power plant and city plumes through evaluation against observations and by studying the impact of different model settings on the results. In the following, the results of the two work packages are summarized separately.

Extended analysis of SMARTCARB simulations

The work package extended the analysis of the synthetic CO₂M satellite observations generated in SMARTCARB-1 for constellations of up to six satellites. The synthetic observations were derived from atmospheric transport simulations performed with the COSMO-GHG model at about 1 km × 1 km resolution for a domain centered over the German capital Berlin for the whole year 2015. Synthetic CO₂ observations were generated for a low-, medium- and high-noise instrument scenario with single sounding precisions of 0.5, 0.7 and 1.0 ppm, respectively, for a ground pixel with vegetation albedo and a solar zenith angle (SZA) of 50° (VEG50 scenario). The NO₂ column densities were assumed to have a low- and high-noise scenario with a single sounding precision of 1.0 and 2.0 × 10¹⁵ molecules per cm⁻² and linearly increase with cloud fraction approximately doubling at 30% cloud fraction. The reference scenario used here are medium-noise CO₂ and high-noise NO₂ observations.

One caveat of the analysis presented in SMARTCARB-1 was that it did not allow drawing firm conclusions on how the ability to quantify emissions from power plants and cities depends on the number of satellites flying in the CO₂M constellation. One reason was that a given satellite orbit with a 250 km wide swath covers a city or power plant at mid-latitudes either once or twice within its 11-day repeat cycle. The simulated constellations therefore had a more or less favorable coverage that arbitrarily depended on the selection of orbit configuration. Furthermore, the number of emission plumes observed during a year under sufficiently cloud-free conditions is small and unevenly distributed in time, which has a large effect on the number of observable plumes for a given orbit. As a result, a constellation of two satellites seemed equally well suited as a constellation of three. For SMARTCARB-2 we simulated additional orbits and created as many constellations of 2, 3, 4, 5 or 6 satellites as possible by permuting the available orbits, in order to enable a more robust assessment of the benefits of a larger constellation size.

The extended analysis for the city of Berlin largely confirmed the conclusions drawn in SMARTCARB-1, but added more insights into the impact of constellation size. Annual emissions were estimated with two approaches, an analytical inversion making the optimistic assumption that atmospheric transport can be perfectly simulated by a model, and a mass-balance approach making the rather pessimistic assumption that useful information on plume location and background concentrations can only be extracted from the satellite observations but not from an atmospheric transport model. The only external information required for the mass-balance approach is an estimation of the mean wind speed within the plume, which can be deduced, e.g., from an operational weather analysis product.

The results of SMARTCARB-2 confirm that only few plumes of a city like Berlin can be detected per satellite per year, which are sufficiently large and suitable for emission estimation, because clouds are frequently blocking the view or because the plume is not sufficiently covered within the swath. On average, **about 6 useful plumes per satellite and year can be detected in satellite NO₂ images, but only about half as many in satellite CO₂ observations, which are more affected by clouds and have a lower signal:noise ratio.** This confirms our previous conclusion that auxiliary NO₂ observations will be key for the CO₂M mission, as they will greatly enhance the number of plumes suitable for CO₂ emission estimation and will allow a better detection of the full extent of the plumes.

Since clouds are the main limiting factor, we analyzed how realistic fractional cloud covers taken from the COSMO-GHG model simulations are. We found that they are highly consistent with the MODIS satellite cloud fraction product, but inconsistent with the MODIS cloud mask product used previously in the ESA project

LOGOFLUX, which has almost twice as many cloud-free pixels. This largely explains why LOGOFLUX found a larger number of plume observations to be suitable, but the lower number presented here is likely more realistic.

CO₂ emissions of Berlin estimated from single plume observations (single overpasses) with the analytical inversion have an average uncertainty of 3.4 Mt yr⁻¹, which corresponds to a relative uncertainty of 17 % of the true emissions of 20 Mt yr⁻¹. For the mass-balance approach, the corresponding numbers are 10 Mt yr⁻¹ and 50%. We expect that future sophisticated methods combining the advantages of mass balance and atmospheric transport model approaches will be able to quantify emissions within this range of uncertainty. Because of the considerable uncertainties of single estimates and because emissions vary with season and from day-to-day, a large number of individual plume estimates per year with good coverage of the different seasons will be needed to reliably determine annual mean emissions. As shown in Fig. 2.9, three satellites will be able to estimate annual mean emissions with an uncertainty of about 2.4 Mt yr⁻¹ (12 %) using the mass-balance approach, and two satellites with an uncertainty of about 3 Mt yr⁻¹ (15 %). In reality, the uncertainties will likely be larger, because true day-to-day emission variability will be higher than in our simulations, where fixed diurnal, day-of-week and seasonal profiles were used.

Another caveat of SMARTCARB-1 was that the methods applied to the estimation of power plant emissions were not fully satisfactory. A Gaussian plume matching method was applied even though the plumes did not always have a Gaussian shape. Furthermore, the plume detection algorithm had difficulties in flagging overlapping plumes from multiple sources and used background values from the simulated background tracer, which did not allow for a realistic estimation of uncertainties associated with the background. These limitations were overcome in SMARTCARB-2, where we further improved the detection algorithm and developed a method capable of estimating background values directly from the satellite observations surrounding the detected plume. Furthermore, we employed the same mass-balance method based on plume slicing that was developed in SMARTCARB-1 for city plumes. The method was applied to simultaneously determine the CO₂ and NO_x emissions of the 15 largest power plants in the domain with reported annual CO₂ emissions between 3.7 Mt yr⁻¹ (Chvaletice, Czech Republic) and 40.3 Mt yr⁻¹ (Jaenschwalde, Germany).

Again, a larger number of plumes could be used for CO₂ emission estimation when the plumes were detected from the NO₂ observations (3-8 plumes per power plant per satellite and year), but the difference from the number of plumes detected from the CO₂ observations (3-5 plumes) was somewhat smaller compared to the city plumes. This suggests that plumes from power plants are more easily detectable because they are spatially more confined and thus more pronounced for the same amount of emitted CO₂. **Median uncertainties of estimated emissions from single overpasses were 31% for CO₂ and 29% for NO_x, respectively, plus a lower threshold for the absolute uncertainty of 2.0 Mt yr⁻¹ and 0.8 kt yr⁻¹. The lower threshold results in a large uncertainty for the smallest power plants with CO₂ emissions of less than 5 Mt yr⁻¹.**

As shown in Fig. 2.20, **annual mean emissions can be estimated with two satellites with a relative uncertainty of less than 32 % for sources larger than 10 Mt yr⁻¹. With three satellites the relative uncertainty reduces to less than 25%. Relative uncertainties strongly increase for sources smaller than 5 Mt yr⁻¹.** Note that all these numbers hold for the case where the plumes are detected from the NO₂ observations. NO₂ observations were found to be critical not only for increasing the number of detectable plumes but also for constraining the shape of the across-plume signals required for computing line densities. This was especially true for the weakest sources.

A constellation of two or three satellites can quantify point sources with an uncertainty smaller than 30% when mean emissions are larger than 12.2 or 6.2 Mt yr⁻¹, respectively. The global map of emission clumps (Wang et al., 2019) lists about 300 or 600 point sources with emissions larger than 12.2 or 6.2 Mt yr⁻¹, respectively. **We therefore expect that adding a third satellite will significantly increase the number of sources that can be quantified with a specific uncertainty.**

A future reduction of NO₂ emissions from power plants, expected as a result of more stringent emission regulations, will have only a limited effect on the detectability of the plumes using the NO₂ observations and hence on CO₂ emission quantification. Only for the weakest sources with annual CO₂ emissions of about 5 Mt yr⁻¹ or lower, a significant reduction of the number of detectable plumes by up to 50 % is expected when NO_x emissions are reduced to 30 % of the

emission levels in 2015. For this scenario, a NO₂ instrument with low measurement noise would clearly be beneficial.

Since NO₂ observations have better signal:noise, are less affected by (thin) clouds, and therefore enable a larger number of successful emission estimates per year, we also investigated the possibility of quantifying CO₂ emissions directly from NO₂ observations, by first estimating NO_x emissions and then applying a representative CO₂:NO_x emission ratio. We found that this approach has two major limitations: First of all, CO₂:NO_x emission ratios need to be determined from those cases where both CO₂ and NO_x emissions can be estimated. The relative uncertainties in these ratios tend to be larger than those of the estimated CO₂ emissions, as they combine the uncertainties in both CO₂ and NO_x emission estimates. Determining a representative ratio will be particularly difficult for cities, since CO₂:NO_x emission ratios are expected to vary with time because the emissions originate from multiple sectors (traffic, heating, industry, etc.) with different emission ratios and different diurnal and seasonal emission cycles. Second, estimating NO_x emissions is challenged by complex atmospheric chemistry, which determines NO:NO₂ concentration ratios and the lifetime of NO_x. Simple assumptions on NO:NO₂ ratios as proposed by Beirle et al. (2011) and applied here may lead to significant biases. In our case, NO_x emissions were systematically overestimated and CO₂:NO_x emission ratios were correspondingly underestimated. Such a systematic bias does not necessarily lead to biased CO₂ estimates, since the biases in NO_x emissions are compensated by those in the CO₂:NO_x emission ratios used for conversion. To better understand the potential and limitations of this approach, it will be necessary to perform full chemistry simulations, which was outside the scope of this study.

Evaluation of plume simulations

Studies directly comparing mesoscale atmospheric transport simulations with airborne high-resolution observations of plumes from power plants or cities are still rare. The COMET aircraft measurement campaign in 2018, which collected a wealth of in situ and remote sensing measurements in the plumes of the power plants Bełchatów in Poland and Jaenschwalde in Germany, provided a unique opportunity for evaluating the COSMO-GHG model. Evaluating how realistically such plumes are simulated allowed us to address the question, to what extent the 'nature runs' conducted in SMARTCARB-1 and used in WP1 are representing reality.

In order to generate realistic simulations for the two power plants, the sources had to be represented very carefully in terms of horizontal position and vertical placement of the initial plume accounting for the rise of the hot, buoyant exhaust. In order to match the position of the plumes as accurately as possible, it was also important to assimilate nearby meteorological observations as routinely done in numerical weather prediction.

The plumes of the two power plants were observed under different meteorological conditions, a highly convective situation in case of Bełchatów and a more stable situation in case of Jaenschwalde, which resulted in largely different plume characteristics both in the simulations and the observations.

For the Bełchatów case, for which sufficient meteorological observations were available, it could be shown that COSMO-GHG captured the vertical profiles of wind direction, wind speed, potential temperature and, hence, atmospheric stability and atmospheric boundary layer structure and extent very well. Only small biases in terms of wind speed and temperature were detected. Overall, this confirms our expectation that COSMO, as a mature numerical weather prediction code, is capable of realistically capturing critical meteorological features for pollution dispersion.

The simulations of the Bełchatów power plant plume indicated a very turbulent flow field in which the released plume dispersed in a meandering way and exhibited puff-like tracer structures, showing clear signs of large eddies being resolved by COSMO at the given resolution of 1 km x 1 km. Since transient eddies at this scale cannot be expected to be simulated exactly at the correct location in time and space, but are rather of a stochastic nature, the comparison against observations remained challenging. Nevertheless, favourable comparison statistics were obtained both for in situ and remote sensing observations. For the latter, plume locations along individual transects were often shifted, a difficulty that partly results from the stochastic flow situation. When looking at the vertical distribution of the simulated plumes, they seemed to be too homogeneous as compared to the observations, indicating that vertical mixing in the model was quicker than in reality. Hence, also the influence of the vertical release profile was limited in this case, showing only minor improvements when using additional plume rise calculations as compared to a default profile. Plume widths were captured fairly well by the model

at short distances but were increasingly over-predicted at larger distances, with an up to three times wider plume simulated at 20 km from the source. The wider model plumes were connected with an under-prediction of maximum plume concentrations. **Simulated temporal variability of the structure of the turbulent plume was very large and especially pronounced in the range up to 15 km from the source. Hence, larger transport uncertainties in this distance range should be considered when plumes in convective regimes are utilised for emission estimation.**

The plume of the Jaenschwalde power plant was much less complex and much more resembled a Gaussian plume shape. Simulated wind speeds were higher and atmospheric boundary layer height lower than for the Bełchatów case. The vertical location of the simulated plume did not agree well with the observations, which suggested an elevated plume, whereas the simulated plume showed a maximum closer to the surface and limited vertical extent. This mismatch in the vertical structure did not improve when using higher release heights. Overall, it may be concluded that vertical mixing was not fast enough in COSMO-GHG in this case, possibly because the model was lagging behind in the development of the convective boundary layer. Despite the less complex plume structure, comparison statistics between model and simulation were not as good as for the Bełchatów case, partly because of the mismatch in the vertical structure. Simulated plume widths were generally larger than observed, but discrepancies did not increase with distance from the source. Largest differences were observed at close range and were most likely due to the limited horizontal resolution of the model. Similarly, plume amplitudes were underestimated at short distances, much less so at larger distances. Hence, it seems that in this case the overall dispersion was not overestimated by the model and mostly the initial plume was too wide due to the limited horizontal resolution of the model.

Generally, we conclude from the analysis that COSMO-GHG simulations can reproduce CO₂ plumes from large point sources with a large degree of realism, despite a tendency to result in wider than observed plumes in convective situations. If this was a general shortcoming of COSMO-GHG, it would be possible that previous nature runs were too pessimistic in terms of detectable plumes, since in reality plumes would stay more compact and exhibit larger vertical column densities for longer distances from the source. However, given that this observation is taken from a single case, it is unclear how much this case can be generalised.

In order to investigate transport uncertainties and to identify favorable model settings, we generated an ensemble of 18 different realizations of the plumes by varying turbulence parameters in COSMO-GHG, by switching meteorological data assimilation on and off, and by releasing the plumes at three different heights. Meteorological data assimilation improved the mean simulated temperature and wind profile with respect to observations in the atmospheric boundary layer, whereas the impact of different turbulence settings on these profiles was very limited.

However, the different turbulence settings resulted in different realizations of the (stochastic) turbulent plume and hence in large variability in simulated plume structure, especially up to distances of about 20 km from the source in the convective case of the Bełchatów power plant plume. Despite these large differences, the model performance statistics in terms of the simulated CO₂ tracer did not reveal a single setup with superior results. Variations in emission release height showed more impact in the less convective Jaenschwalde case, revealing a clearly favourable release height as calculated from plume rise calculations.

The quantification of ensemble spread indicates that different meteorological situations, like the two encountered here, may pose different challenges to atmospheric transport simulations and inverse modelling. On the one hand, the stochastic nature of CO₂ plumes in convective cases may lead to large uncertainties in simulated plume structure in the near field. On the other hand, directional wind shear and changes of wind over time may lead to general changes of plume direction and, hence, larger uncertainties at larger transport distances, especially in the case of compact plumes.

The ensemble of simulations was also used to investigate how well emissions can be quantified from single transects of total column XCO₂ through the plume as observed from satellites like OCO-2 and from single snapshots of 2D XCO₂ images as observed from the future CO2M mission. A fundamental lower limit of the uncertainty was deduced from a method that employed the complete three-dimensional model data and estimated emissions from the horizontal flux through a series of cross sections perpendicular to the plume direction similar to the mass-balance methods presented in WP1. The analysis clearly showed that flux estimation in turbulent plumes is challenging as individual snapshots and transects can differ significantly from the true emissions. Especially estimates from individual plume transects as sampled by satellites like OCO-2 would be

strongly affected by this effect. The range between minimum and maximum flux through different transects was as large as a factor of three. When averaging over many cross sections of the same plume, as would be possible with an imaging satellite, the method was more robust but still resulted in average biases between 5 and 10 % and uncertainties of about 15 %.

When applying the simple analytical inversion based on truth from the CTRL run and on actual simulation from the 18 member ensemble, emissions tended to be underestimated (bias of about 20 %). The reason for this underestimation is that simulated and 'observed' (real) plume do not fully overlap, so that parts of the simulated plume are compared to actual background values in the least squares minimization process. Avoiding such systematic biases will require sophisticated inverse methods, e.g. methods that automatically align simulated and observed plumes.

When applying the mass balance method to perturbed model data (mimicking measurement noise), it increasingly had difficulties in detecting the full extent of very turbulent plumes (Belchatow), resulting in an overestimation of background and underestimation of emissions. Despite largely different plume structures between the different ensemble members, the variability in estimated emissions was surprisingly small, suggesting that uncertainties in the estimation of the background and of the mean wind speed of the plume are more important than uncertainties associated with the turbulent structure of the plume. This is in strong contrast to the analytical inversion, where mismatches between the simulated and observed structure of the plume adds significantly to the uncertainty of the emission estimates.

Recommendations

Topics not sufficiently addressed in SMARTCARB-2 A few topics could not be addressed to the extent originally planned in this project but should be revisited in future studies. For instance, it was planned to compare the temporal emission profiles used in the simulations with actual activity data, in order to quantify the uncertainties in these profiles and their temporal correlations. This would allow a better quantification of the uncertainties in annual mean emissions derived from individual overpasses at a few points in time spread over the year. Although the topic was touched upon in Sect. 2.6, collecting and analyzing suitable activity data turned out to be a huge task. We were able to account for uncertainties associated with hour-to-hour and day-to-day variability of emissions from power plants, but much more work will be needed for cities, where a complex mixture of sources with different temporal profiles and variabilities is present.

Furthermore, it was planned to study how NO₂ observations from the Sentinel-5 mission could assist in quantifying CO₂ emissions. It was already clear from SMARTCARB-1, that the temporal delay between CO₂M and Sentinel-5 precludes the usage of NO₂ observations from Sentinel-5 to guide the detection of the CO₂ plumes observed by CO₂M, but that an NO₂ instrument mounted on CO₂M will be required for this purpose. Another potential use of Sentinel-5 would be to convert estimates of NO₂ emissions into estimates of CO₂ emissions by applying a representative CO₂:NO₂ emission ratio. Sentinel-5 has the advantage of having almost daily coverage, which will allow quantifying NO₂ emissions from many overpasses during a year. However, the emission ratio CO₂:NO₂ would still have to be derived from a few overpasses of CO₂M, and we showed in Sect. 2.7 that these ratios have larger uncertainties than direct estimates of CO₂ emissions. A probably more promising use of Sentinel-5 is to better quantify day-to-day emission variability, assuming that this variability is similar for NO₂ as for CO₂, and to include this information in the uncertainty estimates of annual CO₂ emissions. This aspect should be addressed in a future study, where also the challenges associated with reactive NO_x chemistry should be investigated in much more detail than it was possible here.

Finally, it was planned to compare the COSMO-GHG simulations with other model simulations. This work could only be started but not completed within this project. Empa has initiated an extensive model inter-comparison exercise of power plant plume simulations from 6 different models in collaboration with DLR, MPI-BGC, SPASCIA and the German Federal Office for Radiation Protection. This work is ongoing and will be extended in the EU project CoCO₂ to provide further important insights into transport model requirements and uncertainties.

Measurement campaigns A detailed statistical analysis of the simulations of power plant plumes with observations was not possible, because the number of measurement campaigns is too small to evaluate the

stochastic nature of the plumes. We thus recommend additional measurement campaigns for validating not only CO₂M observations but also for validating model simulations.

The fast temporal changes in the simulated plumes and their distinct characteristics in different atmospheric stability regimes indicates that model performance may strongly depend on the time of day. If model performance should be further optimised for a specific observation window (overpass time), future observations should be taken exactly during this time window. Furthermore, they should cover meteorological conditions that are typical for this time of the day, i.e., a well-developed atmospheric boundary layer but with varying vertical stability and background wind speeds.

The model employed here tended to simulate plumes that were often well-mixed from the surface up to a certain altitude. In contrast, observations suggested elevated plumes, but were lacking any sampling at low altitudes to confirm this conclusively. Future measurement campaigns should therefore try to include in-situ observations over the full vertical extent of the plume down to (or almost) the surface. When comparing plume observations at very close range from any point source, Eulerian models will always be limited by their grid resolution. A more suitable comparison can be achieved at distances several times that of the grid resolution (e.g. 10-20 km for a model with 1-2 km resolution). Future measurement campaigns should put a focus on this distance range and less onto the short range. On the other hand, emission plumes of weak sources are only detectable close to the source (<10 km), which requires validation close to the source, but this also likely requires model simulations with higher spatial resolution.

Urban plumes are more complex and may feature multiple sub-plumes from dominant point sources. Currently, there are only a few NO₂ observations from airborne imaging spectrometers available over cities, but no corresponding CO₂ observations. In order to better understand the relation between NO₂ and CO₂ over cities and the impact of reactive chemistry on the evolution of NO₂ in the plume, aircraft measurement campaigns with simultaneous imaging of the two compounds would be highly desirable.

Synthetic Level-1/-2 observations The synthetic CO₂M and Sentinel-5 observations generated in SMART-CARB focused on a long time series at high spatial resolution. The simulations were therefore limited to a regional domain in Europe and it was not feasible to conduct computationally expensive full-chemistry simulations that included complex NO_x and aerosol chemistry. As a result, several aspects of CO₂M could not be investigated sufficiently. Firstly, it remains unclear how the results transfer to other regions. Secondly, the study of the quantitative use of NO₂ observations was limited as NO₂:NO ratios, NO₂:NO_x conversion factors, and the NO_x decay times were insufficiently known. Thirdly, the impact of aerosols on random and systematic errors in the retrievals were not included in the synthetic observations.

To cover these aspects, we therefore recommend to generate additional synthetic observations of cities, power plants and other point sources that use kilometer-scale full chemistry transport simulations. Since the generation of long time series is computationally prohibitive, a library of case studies could be created using small model domains for various city and point sources. Synthetic observations should include both random and systematic (spatially and temporally correlated) error components caused, for instance by aerosols, surface reflectance and orography. For this it will be required to create synthetic CO₂M Level-1 data using radiative transfer models for the CO₂ and NO₂ imaging spectrometers and considering the measurements from the Multi Angle Polarimeter (MAP).

To be suitable as input for quantifying retrieval uncertainties, scenarios should cover different observation geometries (nadir and glint for different solar zenith angles), a realistic range of surface reflectances and aerosol mixtures (urban, desert dust, biomass burning, etc.). Furthermore, the scenarios should cover different seasons, climate zones, and NO_x chemistry regimes. CO₂ and NO_x emissions should consider a range of source strengths and emission ratios. Furthermore, the power plant cases should include different release heights and types, i.e. via stack or cooling tower, as cooling towers including significant emissions of water vapor. For cities, cases should include different ratios of emission sectors (traffic, residential, industries etc.) as they modify CO₂:NO_x emission ratios and vertical emission profiles. The synthetic Level-1/-2 observations can be used to study uncertainties at local scale, for example, due to aerosols and water vapor in the emission plume and should also an analysis of three-dimensional radiative transfer effects on plume imaging and emission quantification (Schwaerzel et al., 2020).

Improved quantification of point sources using additional data sources The mass-balance approach applied in this project resulted in relatively large uncertainties in estimated annual emissions because of (1) uncertainties in the data-driven approach (e.g. assumption of steady state conditions and spatially smooth background fields) and (2) limited information on the temporal variability of emissions. The first point can potentially be improved using a full inversion system that can incorporate a priori model information. On the other hand, any model-based inversion system will likely have to incorporate a plume detection algorithm to be able to align the simulated plume with the observed plume. Simulating the direction and shape of the plumes with the accuracy needed to achieve a strong overlap will remain a major challenge for atmospheric transport models due to uncertainties in plume rise, in mesoscale flows (e.g., near coastlines), and due to turbulent fluctuations. To improve our knowledge about temporal variability of emissions, additional data sources (e.g., activity data, ground-based networks, and geostationary satellites) should be utilized. This will not only enable an improved description of uncertainties associated with temporal variability of emissions (between individual satellite overpasses) but could also be used to reduce these uncertainties. Furthermore, the usage of long-term averages (instead of using single satellite images) may have the potential to improve emission quantification especially for weak point sources.

1. Introduction

1.1 Context

In April 2016, ESA established the CO₂ Monitoring Task Force Group to advise on the implementation of a space component meeting the needs of a European contribution to a global CO₂ emission monitoring and verification support system. A CO₂ satellite with imaging capability complemented by atmospheric transport and inverse modelling was identified as a key component of such a system (Ciais et al., 2015; Pinty et al., 2018). The system would allow for observing CO₂ plumes of emission hot spots such as large cities and power plants and, thereby, for quantifying the emissions from the images captured during single satellite overpasses (Bovensmann et al., 2010; Pillai et al., 2016; Broquet et al., 2018; Velazco et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2020). However, a major challenge is the interference of biospheric CO₂, which complicates the attribution of measured CO₂ variations to anthropogenic emissions. Furthermore, CO₂ enhancements from city and point sources are of similar magnitude as the expected single sounding precision of the CO₂ observations. Therefore, measurements of auxiliary trace gases co-emitted from fossil fuel combustion such as carbon monoxide (CO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) were proposed to help separate the anthropogenic from the biospheric CO₂ emissions as well as detecting the emission plumes.

In order to study the use of such auxiliary measurements in detail, the SMARTCARB project was proposed. In the first phase of the project conducted in the years 2017-2018 (Kuhlmann et al., 2019b), the potential synergies of measurements of CO and NO₂ and the impact of different satellite specifications (e.g. overpass time, spatial coverage, time separation between measurements of CO₂ and those of CO and NO₂ in case they are measured on different satellites) were assessed (Brunner et al., 2019; Kuhlmann et al., 2019a, 2020a). The tools for addressing these questions were high-resolution atmospheric transport simulations and inverse methods combined with synthetic satellite observations derived from the simulations. The main outcome of the study was a set of requirements for accuracy, coverage and other factors affecting the satellite measurements to be able to quantify the CO₂ emissions of individual point sources to a certain level of accuracy. The SMARTCARB study was extended to a second phase (SMARTCARB-2, 2019-2020) to enable a more robust assessment of the performance of different instrument and satellite configurations and a better assessment of the quality of the simulations.

1.2 Objectives of the present document

This document describes the results of the additional analyses conducted in two work packages in the second phase of the SMARTCARB project. The objective of the first work package was a further development of the analysis methods and an extended investigation of the simulations conducted in SMARTCARB-1. In work package 2, additional simulations were performed for selected cases, in order to evaluate the simulations against observations and to better characterize transport uncertainties in the model and their impact on the estimated emissions.

2. Work package 1: Extended analysis of SMARTCARB simulations

2.1 Objectives of the work package

This work package builds on the COSMO-GHG simulations and synthetic satellite observations generated in the first phase of the SMARTCARB project (Kuhlmann et al., 2019b). The SMARTCARB-1 data package is available online (Kuhlmann et al., 2020b). In this extension of the project, additional analyses of the simulations were conducted to provide a more robust assessment of the performance of different instrument and satellite configurations. The work package consists of the following six tasks, which are addressed in sections 2.3-2.8 of this document:

Task 1: Improved plume detection algorithm Develop an improved plume detection algorithm to provide a robust estimate of plume extent, orientation, and background levels.

Task 2: Robust emission estimation based on Monte Carlo experiments Simulate multiple different constellations of satellites varying in the starting longitude of the first satellite to provide a more robust estimate of the coverage of a given target and of its emissions. This is necessary because the spatial coverage of an individual city or power plant by a given constellation of satellites depends strongly on the initial equator crossing longitude of the first satellite.

Task 3: Improved quantification of power plant emissions by plume slicing Quantify power plant emissions with the plume slicing/balance approach developed and applied in SMARTCARB-1 for city plumes. In SMARTCARB-1, emissions from power plants were estimated using a Gaussian plume matching, which proved to be associated with high uncertainties due to the often non-Gaussian behavior of plumes.

Task 4: Improved estimation of annual mean emissions and uncertainties The accuracy of an annual mean estimate derived from individual overpasses on a small number of days depends critically on how well the temporal variability of emissions can be described. In this task, temporal variability of emissions is accounted when estimating annual mean emissions by considering day-to-day and hour-to-hour variability of emissions.

Task 5: Quantitative usage of NO₂ for CO₂ source estimation Estimate CO₂ emissions from satellite NO₂ measurements by applying known CO₂:NO₂ emission ratios. Here, CO₂:NO₂ emission ratios are estimated from overpasses of the CO2M satellites with strong plume signals. CO₂ emissions can then be derived from the NO₂ observations in both strong and weak plumes.

Task 6: Consideration of expected future reduction in NO₂ emissions from power plants Evaluate, how the expected future reductions in NO₂ emissions due to improved exhaust gas after-treatment will affect the utility of additional NO₂ measurements.

2.2 SMARTCARB simulations and synthetic satellite observations

Here we provide a brief summary of the simulations conducted in SMARTCARB-1, which provided the basis for the analyses in this work package. Atmospheric transport simulations of CO₂ and NO_x were performed with the COSMO-GHG model at about 1 km × 1 km resolution for a domain centered over the German capital Berlin for the whole year 2015. Lateral boundary conditions, anthropogenic emissions and biospheric fluxes

were accounted for as realistically as possible to generate a 'nature run' of CO₂ and NO_x concentrations that should closely resemble true atmospheric conditions. For computational efficiency, NO_x was simulated as a tracer with a constant exponential decay time of 4 hours rather than considering its complex photochemistry using an expensive chemistry scheme. The simulations are described in more detail in Brunner et al. (2019); Kuhlmann et al. (2019a, 2020a).

Synthetic observations were then generated from the high resolution simulations for a hypothetical constellation of up to six CO2M satellites using satellite orbit simulations and applying different levels of noise according to different precision requirements as specified by ESA. The satellites were assumed to fly in a sun-synchronous orbit with an overpass time of 11:30 local time and with a 250 km wide swath. In each constellation, satellites were spaced with equal angular distance in a common orbit. As an example, Figure 2.1 shows a constellation of six satellites. A constellation of 2 or 3 satellites could then be composed, for example, of the satellites 'a' and 'd' or 'a', 'c' and 'e', respectively. A constellation of four and five equally-spaced satellites cannot be created from these six satellites but required additional orbit simulations. Therefore, in total, 12 unique satellite orbits were simulated to generate constellations of one to six satellites.

Figure 2.1: Sketch of a constellation of six CO2M satellites (a-f) equally spaced in a common sun-synchronous orbit.

To generate the synthetic observations of XCO₂ and tropospheric columns of NO₂, the model simulated fields were sampled along the 250-km wide swath of the 12 orbits at 2 km × 2 km spatial resolution. Random noise was then computed and added to the simulated XCO₂ pixel values using the error parametrization of Buchwitz et al. (2013) and assuming a low-, medium- and high-noise instrument scenario with single sounding precisions of 0.5, 0.7 and 1.0 ppm, respectively, for a ground pixel with vegetation albedo and a solar zenith angle (SZA) of 50° (VEG50 scenario). Systematic errors were not included. The NO₂ column densities were assumed to have a low- and high-noise scenario with a single sounding precision of 1.0 and 2.0 × 10¹⁵ molecules per cm⁻² and linearly increase with cloud fraction approximately doubling at 30% cloud fraction. XCO₂ observations were rigorously cloud filtered using a cloud threshold of 1%. A cloud threshold of 30% was used for the NO₂ observations, which can tolerate larger cloud fractions. Cloud fractions were taken from the same COSMO-GHG simulation that also provided the CO₂ and NO₂ fields. If not explicitly mentioned, results are reported for a reference scenario, which uses medium-noise CO₂ observations and high-noise NO₂ observations.

2.3 Improved plume detection algorithm

A plume detection algorithm was developed in SMARTCARB-1 to identify coherent structures of satellite pixels where the CO₂ or NO₂ values are enhanced above the background field and to assign them to potential sources (Kuhlmann et al., 2019a). This algorithm was also applied here for the detection of the plumes of the city of Berlin (Task 2.4). An important limitation of this algorithm was that it used the simulated background tracer to estimate the background field within the plume, so that it could not be applied to satellite observations where this information is missing. Furthermore, the algorithm required a lot of fine-tuning and visual control. In order to overcome these limitations, an improved version of the algorithm was developed here, which does not depend on model simulated background fields anymore. Furthermore, the algorithm can now detect a predefined list of sources, instead of a single source, and automatically recognizes overlapping plumes from multiple sources. The improved algorithm was applied to detect and quantify the emissions of power plant plumes (Task 2.5).

The improved algorithm consists of four steps: Firstly, it detects satellite pixels whose measurement values are enhanced above the background field. Secondly, the detected pixels are spatially combined to regions. Thirdly, these regions are assigned to sources. Finally, for each detected plume a centerline is calculated as well as a polygon, which contains the detected pixels and thus describes the extent of the plume.

In the first step, a signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is computed for each satellite pixel:

$$SNR = \frac{X_{\text{obs}} - X_{\text{bg}}}{\sqrt{\sigma_{\text{rand}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{sys}}^2}} \geq z_q \quad (2.1)$$

where X_{obs} is the satellite observation, X_{bg} is the background field, σ_{rand} and σ_{sys} are the local random and systematic errors in the satellite image. The SNR can be used in a statistical z-test that computes the likelihood that the XCO₂ or NO₂ value of a pixel is enhanced above the background. z_q is the threshold for which the SNR is significantly larger than the background with a probability q (see Kuhlmann et al., 2019a, for details). In this study, the threshold z_q was set to 2.33, which corresponds to a probability q of 0.99.

Instead of taking X_{obs} as the value of the satellite pixel at this location, it was computed as a local mean averaged over surrounding pixels. In the first version of the algorithm, the local mean was computed using an uniform filter with neighborhoods of different sizes. In the improved version, a Gaussian filter of width σ_g is used, which has the advantage that it provides a gentler and more adjustable smoothing making the algorithm more adaptable for different plume sizes.

In the first version of the algorithm, the background field was derived from a simulated background tracer. In the improved version, it is computed by applying a median filter to the (synthetic) satellite image. The filter computes the background as the local median in a 100×100 pixels window, assuming that the majority of pixels in the window consists of background pixels without significant enhancements.

The random noise σ_{rand}^2 was taken from the single sounding precision of the XCO₂ or NO₂ observations. The systematic error σ_{sys}^2 can be interpreted as a threshold for variance in the background, e.g. caused by CO₂ variations due to biospheric fluxes, or also as a smallest possible error for a very large filter. In this study, σ_{sys} was set to 0.2 ppm for XCO₂ and 0.5×10^{15} molecules per cm⁻² for NO₂ observations.

In the second step, a standard labeling algorithm is used to connect neighboring pixels with enhanced values, i.e. pixels for which Eq. (2.1) is true. Enhanced pixels were considered connected if they were horizontal, vertical or diagonal neighbours.

In the third step, a region of enhanced pixels is assigned to a point source, if the pixels overlap with a circle of radius 5 km surrounding the source. In the first version of the algorithm this was only possible for a single source. The improved version of the algorithm is now able to detect multiple sources contributing to a plume. For this purpose we created a list of all point sources in the model domain that have NO_x emissions larger than 3 kt yr⁻¹ based on the TNO/MACC-3 inventory. Figure 2.2 shows a map of the XCO₂ field simulated for 3 November 2015 and the location of the 15 largest source that have annual NO_x emissions larger than the threshold, which together account for 28% of total CO₂ emissions and 17% of NO_x emissions in the domain, respectively. The sources and their emissions are also listed in Table 2.1.

Finally, for each detected plume, a centerline is fitted as a two-dimensional curve to the detected pixels. We also include pixels within 5 km of the plume with low weight to make the fit more robust especially at the start and end of the plume. In addition, we add the source location with high weight to force the centerline through that point.

Figure 2.3 shows an example plume for a point source with detected pixels and centerline. Longitude and latitude of the pixels are converted to a plume coordinate system consisting of arc length of the centerline from the source location and distance from the centerline (see Kuhlmann et al., 2020a, for details). A polygon is drawn around the detected pixels whose width is the maximum width of a detected plume rounded up to the next 2 km. In along-plume direction, the polygon’s length extends from the source to the end of the detected plume rounded up to the next full 5 km. The polygon is subdivided in 5 km wide sub-polygons in along-plume direction. In addition, we draw a second polygon from 2 to 12 km upstream of the source.

Figure 2.2: Spatial distribution of the largest point sources in the COSMO-GHG domain (white dots). The largest 15 point sources are labelled with their names. The image shows an XCO₂ model field on 2 November 2015.

Table 2.1: CO₂ and NO_x source strengths of the largest point sources (>3.0 kt yr⁻¹ annual mean) in the study area according to the TNO/MACC-3 inventory used in this study. The source strengths shown are at satellite overpass time (10:30 UTC) that are about 20% higher than annual mean emissions. The values are total anthropogenic emissions in a COSMO grid cell (about 1 km × 1 km) and therefore can be higher than the facility emissions. These 15 point sources represent 28% and 17% of total CO₂ and NO_x emissions in the model domain, respectively.

Point source (Country code)	CO ₂ [Mt yr ⁻¹]	NO _x [kt yr ⁻¹]	CO ₂ -to-NO _x emission ratio
Jänschwalde (D)	40.3	32.6	1238
Boxberg (D)	23.1	18.6	1238
Lippendorf (D)	18.5	14.9	1238
Prunéřov (CZ)	13.4	13.2	1012
Počerady (CZ)	10.9	10.8	1012
Turów (PL)	10.6	15.9	665
Schwarze Pumpe (D)	9.9	8.0	1238
Dolna Odra (PL)	9.3	11.8	789
Opole (PL)	8.8	11.2	789
Patnów (PL)	7.1	10.6	665
Schkopau (D)	7.0	5.5	1257
Mělník (CZ)	6.1	6.1	1012
Heyden (D)	6.1	4.9	1257
Staudinger (D)	5.8	4.6	1257
Chvaletice (CZ)	3.7	3.6	1012

Figure 2.3: Sketch of a detected CO₂ plume with detected pixels, centerline, and the polygons up- and downstream of the source that can be used for computing CO₂ fluxes.

2.4 Robust emission estimation based on Monte Carlo Experiments

2.4.1 Introduction

The analysis of how well emissions can be quantified as a function of the size of the satellite constellation presented in SMARTCARB-1 was not very robust due to the fact that different satellites have a different spatial and temporal coverage of the model domain centered over Berlin. As an example, Figure 2.4 shows the global and European coverage of satellite ‘a’ within its 11-day repeat cycle. In the SMARTCARB model domain, the number of overpasses over a given location is either once or twice per repeat cycle resulting in the stripes in the figure. The location of these stripes is shifted in west-east direction for the different satellites in the constellation.

Due to frequent cloud coverage, the number of observable cloud-free plumes per year is relatively small. The number is even smaller if the plumes need to be detected from noisy CO_2 or NO_2 observations, because detection is not always possible when signal-to-noise ratios are small or when broken clouds cover a substantial part of the plume. This is especially true for CO_2 observations, since the amplitude of the plume signal is often of the same magnitude as the measurement noise of the instrument. This makes the detectability depend strongly on the random noise pattern applied to the synthetic observations.

The largely different temporal and spatial coverage of the model domain by different satellite orbits results in large differences in the number of detectable plumes between different constellation sizes but also between constellations of the same size composed of different satellites. For example, satellite ‘c’ passes over Berlin only once during the cycle, meaning that constellations with this specific satellite always have a comparatively low coverage. In the SMARTCARB-1 project this led to the counter-intuitive (and non-satisfactory) conclusion that two satellites had better coverage than three satellites.

In order to overcome these limitations and to obtain more robust results, we created as many combinations of satellite orbits as possible for constellations between one and six satellites to study the statistical variability of observable and detectable plumes. Furthermore, we applied different noise patterns to the same swath image to check the sensitivity of the plume detection algorithm to noise patterns. Finally, we studied the effect of cloud filtering on the number of observable/detectable plumes when using three different cloud products, the MODIS cloud mask product, the MODIS cloud fraction product, or the cloud fractions from the COSMO-GHG simulations. The latter has been used in the SMARTCARB-1 study.

Figure 2.4: Spatial coverage of one CO_2M satellite within its 11-day repeat cycle (a) globally and (b) over Europe. The white square marks the COSMO-GHG model domain in which the number of overpasses is either one or two. The exact locations of the "stripes" are arbitrary and depend on the equator starting longitude (here: 0°E) of the satellite (Kuhlmann et al., 2019a, Figure 2).

2.4.2 Monte Carlo experiments for plume detection

The results presented in this section are described in more detail in Kuhlmann et al. (2019a) and are only summarized in the following. The number of observable cloud-free, but not necessarily detectable, plumes for

Berlin is shown in Figure 2.5 for CO₂ and NO₂ observations using a cloud threshold of 1% and 30%, respectively. The city plume was considered observable when at least 100 pixels of the simulated tracer representing only emissions from the city were above a threshold, which was derived from a typical variability in the background. The most limiting factor for the number of observable plumes was found to be the cloud coverage rather than the signal of the plume above the background variability. The vertical bars show the number of observable plumes for different constellations using equal angular distance orbits. The error bars show the 1 σ standard deviations when considering all possible combinations of the 12 unique orbits available but ignoring the equally-spaced constraint. The result shows that for the equally-spaced satellites, the number of observable plumes is not always increasing with constellation size. For example, the number of observable plumes during the whole year is equal for a constellation of 2 and 3 satellites. The individual satellites are in this case ‘a’ and ‘d’ as well as ‘a’, ‘c’ and ‘e’ with ‘c’ covering Berlin only once within 11 days. The effect is larger when considering individual months. However, the difference is within the expected variability when considering different orbit configurations. A larger number of plumes is observable for NO₂, because background variability is smaller compared to CO₂. Because statistical fluctuations are smaller when the numbers are larger, the number of observable plumes increases more steadily with the size of the constellation.

Figure 2.5: Number of cloud-free plumes per month of the city of Berlin with at least 100 pixels for (a) CO₂ and (b) NO₂. The cloud threshold is 1% for CO₂, and 30% for NO₂ observations. Error bars are obtained by computing the standard deviation for all possible combinations of the 12 simulated satellite orbits for a given constellation size. The average number of expected plumes per satellite per year is 8 and 17 for the CO₂ and NO₂ instrument, respectively. Adapted from Kuhlmann et al. (2019a).

When detecting the plumes from noisy CO₂ or NO₂ observations using the plume detection algorithm presented earlier, the number of detectable plumes is smaller than the number of observable plumes. A plume is considered detectable when more than 100 pixels can be detected by the algorithm. A minimum size of 100 pixels was considered necessary for a plume emanating from a city with a horizontal diameter of the order of 40 km.

Figure 2.6 shows an example of the detection of the plume of the city of Berlin based on CO₂ and NO₂ observations from CO2M and Sentinel-5 for different instrument scenarios (see Kuhlmann et al. (2019b) for a

detailed description of the noise scenarios). The outlines of the real plumes are overlaid as solid and dashed lines for CO_2 and NO_2 , respectively. The CO_2 and NO_2 plumes do not fully overlap because of the $X\text{CO}_2$ and NO_2 thresholds used for defining the plume extent and because the relative share of sources with different vertical emission profiles is different for the two species. Satellite pixels that have been detected by the plume detection algorithm are shown as black crosses, and the number of detected pixels (median of all 20 noise realizations) are presented in the legend. On average, a CO_2 instrument detects 116 ± 46 , 48 ± 40 and 24 ± 30 pixels with noise scenarios σ_{VEG50} of 0.5, 0.7 and 1.0 ppm, respectively (Fig. 2.6a and b). The NO_2 instrument can detect a much larger number of pixels, i.e., 1242 ± 99 and 1203 ± 155 in the case of the low-noise and the high-noise instrument scenarios, respectively (Fig. 2.6c). This example shows that especially for the CO_2 observations with high noise, the plume detection can fail frequently.

Figure 2.6: Example of plume detection with CO2M’s CO_2 and NO_2 instrument and Sentinel-5’s NO_2 instrument on 21 April 2015. Significant pixels detected by the algorithm are highlighted as black crosses. The outlines of the true CO_2 and NO_2 plumes based on the X_{BER} tracers are overlaid as solid and dashed lines, respectively. (a) Low-noise CO_2 instrument with $\sigma_{\text{VEG50}} = 0.5$ ppm. (b) high-noise CO_2 instrument with $\sigma_{\text{VEG50}} = 1.0$ ppm. (c) High-noise NO_2 instrument on the CO2M satellite with $\sigma_{\text{ref}} = 2 \times 10^{15}$ molecules cm^{-2} . (d) NO_2 instrument on Sentinel-5. Adapted from Kuhlmann et al. (2019a).

Figure 2.7 shows the number of detectable plumes per month for Berlin. A plume was considered detectable when on average more than 100 pixels were detected for the 20 realisations with different random noise patterns. Since the number of detectable plumes per month is quite small, the results are highly sensitive to the specific orbit configuration. As discussed earlier, a constellation of two satellites appears to detect more plumes than three, but this result is only due to an unfavorable orbit for the constellation with three satellites and unfavorable cloud cover. When considering all possible combinations, the figure confirms the expectation that the number of detectable plumes generally increases with the number of satellites, but the statistical noise can mask this tendency. On average, about 3 plumes can be detected per satellite and year from the CO_2 observations, and about twice as many from the NO_2 observations.

Figure 2.7: Number of detectable CO₂ plumes with at least 100 pixels for a constellation of one to six satellites with (a) CO₂ observations with low noise ($\sigma_{\text{VEG50}} = 0.5$ ppm) and (b) an NO₂ observations with high noise ($\sigma_{\text{ref}} = 2 \times 10^{15}$ molecules cm⁻²) (Kuhlmann et al., 2019a, Figure 11).

2.4.3 Monte Carlo experiments for estimating city emissions

Here we analyze the impact of the number of satellites on the ability to estimate the CO₂ emissions of the city of Berlin considering all satellite overpasses during the year 2015. The analysis is limited to constellations of 1, 2, 3 and 6 satellites that are spaced with equal angular distance in a common orbit (see Figure 2.1). Emissions were estimated with an atmospheric inversion considering only the random noise of the satellite instrument (analytical inversion) and a data-driven mass-balance approach.

The analytical inversion estimates CO₂ emissions by scaling the simulated CO₂ signature of the city plume to match the CO₂ observations. The plume signature was taken from the same COSMO-GHG simulations used for generating the synthetic satellite observations but assumes constant emissions. The method therefore assumes that the CO₂ signature and the CO₂ background field can be simulated perfectly with a model. The mass-balance approach estimates CO₂ emissions from line densities that are computed from the CO₂ satellite image by integrating the city’s CO₂ signal perpendicular to the mean wind direction. The location and extent of the city plume were detected by the plume detection algorithm developed in SMARTCARB-1 (Kuhlmann et al., 2019a). The CO₂ signal was obtained by subtracting the CO₂ background field from the observations. The background was estimated from the CO₂ observations surrounding the detected plume. Both approaches are described in detail in Kuhlmann et al. (2020a). The approaches are considered as spanning the range between pessimistic and optimistic assumptions regarding the capabilities of atmospheric transport models and therefore should provide a realistic range of uncertainties for different constellations. Annual emissions were obtained by fitting a low-order spline to the individual emission estimates to account for the temporal variability of emissions. All results shown here are for medium-noise scenario ($\sigma_{\text{VEG50}} = 0.70$ ppm).

The precision for a single CO₂ emission estimate is about 3.4 Mt yr⁻¹ for the analytical inversion and about 10 Mt yr⁻¹ with the mass-balance approach for both CO₂ and NO₂-based plume detection. The number of successful estimates over the whole year 2015 ranged from 5 to 17 for a single satellite using the analytical

inversion. For the mass-balance approach the number of successful estimates ranged from 1 to 7 using CO₂ and from 0 to 10 using NO₂ for detecting the plume. Figure 2.8 shows the corresponding estimates of annual emissions for different constellations. For the analytical inversion both constant and time-varying emissions were analysed. In both cases, annual mean emissions could be estimated quite well even with only one satellite. The estimated uncertainty of the annual estimates improves from 1.1 Mt yr⁻¹ (5.5%) to 0.3 Mt yr⁻¹ (1.5%) for 1 to 6 satellites due to the larger number of successful individual estimates. In contrast, estimating annual emissions by mass-balance is very difficult, if only the CO₂ observations are available for detecting the location of the plumes. For a single satellite, the number of overpasses with successful emission estimates is too small to fit a seasonal cycle in nearly all cases and even with two or three satellites the precision is low with about 8.8 Mt yr⁻¹ (44%). The situation significantly improves when additional NO₂ observations are used for plume detection. A single satellite can estimate annual emissions in five out of six cases with an average precision of 5.1 Mt yr⁻¹ (26%) due to the better temporal coverage. The average precision increases to 4.4 Mt yr⁻¹ (22%) and 2.5 Mt yr⁻¹ (13%) for constellations of two and three satellites, respectively. For the mass-balance approach, the annual emissions are slightly overestimated, because of low temporal coverage in winter and because the method is also sensitive to emissions outside of Berlin.

Figure 2.8: Upper row: Estimated annual emissions at satellite overpass time for the analytical inversion with (a) constant and (b) time-varying CO₂ emissions. Lower row: Estimated emissions using a mass-balance approach applied to plumes detected from (c) CO₂ and (d) NO₂ observations. The annual emissions were estimated from different constellations of 1, 2, 3 and 6 satellites with letters a to f indicating the six different satellites. The number of overpasses with successful plume detection and emission estimation are shown in brackets. If the number of individual estimates is too small for computing a seasonal cycle, values are marked with a cross. Error bars show the precision computed from the individual emission estimates at satellite overpass. The legend shows the mean error for each constellation size. The analysis is based on CO₂ observations with medium noise ($\sigma_{\text{VEG50}} = 0.7$ ppm) and NO₂ observations with high noise ($\sigma_{\text{ref}} = 2 \times 10^{15}$ molecules cm⁻²).

Table 2.2 shows the range of estimated random uncertainties for these cases together with the uncertainty estimated in SMARTCARB-1, which agrees quite well with the estimates here. Especially for one and two satellites, the numbers reveal a large spread between individual constellations of the same size. For more robust conclusions it is therefore necessary to combine the results of all possible constellations of a given size. Since the uncertainty of the annual emissions depends mainly on the number of satellites, we can roughly estimate the uncertainty of the annual mean from the uncertainty of the estimates for single overpasses using different combinations of satellites. Figure 2.9 shows the expected uncertainty with the analytical inversion and the mass-balance approach as a function of the number of satellites. The mean random uncertainty for each method was computed by dividing the estimated uncertainty of a single estimate by the square root of the number of estimates. Note that this assumes that the temporal variability of emissions (e.g. the seasonal cycle) is known or can be estimated precisely from the individual estimates. This assumption likely underestimates the true uncertainty for a single satellite. The error bars denote the range of this number when considering all possible combination of the six satellites (a-f). The dark gray area between the two lines shows the average expected range of precision for the two methods for a city with similar temporal coverage as Berlin. Due to the wide range of successful estimates per satellite, the precision for a single city may be worse and could also be within the light gray range. To achieve a precision of 10%, probably three or more satellites are necessary.

Table 2.2: Range of random uncertainty of estimated annual emissions for constellation sizes shown in Figure 2.8. The estimated precision in SMARTCARB-1 are also shown.

Number of satellites	SMARTCARB-2				SMARTCARB-1
	1	2	3	6	6
Analytical inversion (time-varying emissions)	0.5 - 2.5	0.4 - 0.6	~ 0.4	0.3	0.4
CO ₂ -based plume detection	6.2 - ∞	4.4 - 13.4	3.8 - 14.0	2.7	2.4
NO ₂ -based plume detection	3.6 - ∞	2.5 - 7.4	~ 2.5	1.7	1.5

Figure 2.9: Estimated precision of Berlin’s annual CO₂ emissions for different number of satellites. The precision is computed from the single estimate precision of 3.4 Mt yr⁻¹ and 10.0 Mt yr⁻¹ for analytical inversion and mass-balance approach, respectively, divided by the square root of individual estimates. The markers use the mean number of estimates and the error bars show the range considering all possible combinations of six satellites. The dark gray area is the expected range of uncertainty given by the two methods. Note that the figure ignores the systematic errors in the estimate and that a sufficient number of estimates is required to fit the seasonal cycle.

2.4.4 Cloud filtering

Clouds have a very strong influence of the number of observable plumes, because CO₂ observations require a strict cloud filtering. The number of cloud-free CO₂ plumes was found to be significantly smaller in SMARTCARB-1 than in the previous LOGOFLUX studies. For Berlin, between 3 and 13 cloud-free CO₂

plumes were identified for a single satellite with a 250-km wide swath, while Pillai et al. (2016) identified 41 potentially useful cases for an orbit with a 500 km wide swath. It is difficult to compare these two numbers, because of the different swath widths and the different definitions of “usefulness”. However, even under the assumption that the number of observable plumes is proportional to the swath width, significantly fewer plumes were identified in SMARTCARB-1.

Figure 2.10: Monthly fractions of cloud-free pixels using cloud masks from COSMO-GHG and MODIS with different spatial resolution (1 km and 5 km) and (a) 1% and (b) 30% cloud fraction as threshold (from the supplement of Kuhlmann et al., 2019a).

A major difference between LOGOFLUX and SMARTCARB is the data product used for masking cloudy pixels. In LOGOFLUX, the MODIS cloud mask product was used, which employs a series of visible and infrared thresholds and consistency tests to specify confidence that a MODIS pixel is cloud-free (Ackerman et al., 2017). The cloud mask product is available globally at 1 km resolution making it suitable for masking cloudy pixels in synthetic CO₂ observations at 4 km² resolution. In SMARTCARB, cloud screening was not only necessary for CO₂ but also for NO₂ and CO observations, which can tolerate larger cloud fractions. Applying different thresholds requires a cloud fraction product rather than a cloud mask product. However, the MODIS cloud product is only available at 5 km resolution (Platnick et al., 2017). In the SMARTCARB study, total cloud fraction was therefore computed from the COSMO-GHG simulation output rather than from MODIS.

The different cloud masking approaches were compared by computing the number of cloud-free pixels in the SMARTCARB model domain using the COSMO-GHG simulations, the MODIS cloud mask product, and the MODIS cloud fraction product with a threshold of 1% and 30% required for CO₂ and NO₂ observations, respectively. The COSMO-GHG cloud fractions were spatially averaged over the MODIS pixels. Figure 2.10 shows the monthly fractions of cloud-free pixels. The values agree very well between COSMO-GHG and the MODIS cloud fraction product for both thresholds. In contrast, the fraction of cloud-free pixels is about twice as high for the MODIS cloud mask product. The result is consistent with a MODIS validation study showing that the cloud mask product is not very sensitive to optically thin clouds (Ackerman et al., 2008). The overestimation of cloud-free pixels when using the MODIS cloud mask product likely explains the much higher number of useful plumes identified in the LOGOFLUX study. The lower numbers presented in SMARTCARB are likely more realistic.

2.5 Improved quantification of power plant emissions by plume slicing

The domain covered by the COSMO-GHG simulations includes several large point sources (Figure 2.2). Plume detection and emissions quantification was performed for the 15 largest point sources in the domain (all being power plants), which are labelled in the figure by their names. Plumes were detected with the improved detection algorithm described in Sect. 2.3.

2.5.1 Method

2.5.1.1 Mass-balance approach

The mass-balance approach is a data-driven method that estimates the emissions of a source from the difference between the fluxes into and out of a volume containing the source. Here, the method was applied to estimate CO₂ or NO_x emissions from a single satellite image. Fluxes out of the volume were computed as the fluxes through the sub-polygons determined by the plume detection algorithm downstream of the source. Under the assumption of steady-state conditions, this is equivalent to the emission, since the inflow upstream of the source is zero. The only additional information required is an estimate of the wind speed inside the plume.

The fluxes are the product of line densities and wind speed. Line densities are computed by integrating the trace gas signal of a source perpendicular to the plume’s center. To obtain the trace gas signal attributable to the source, the background field needs to be subtracted from the satellite observations. The CO₂ and NO₂ backgrounds are estimated from the pixels surrounding the plume assuming that they are smooth. First, the detected pixels of the plume as well as other pixels marked as significantly enhanced above the background by the plume detection algorithm were removed from the observations. Next, the gaps were filled using normalized convolution with a Gaussian filter with $\sigma = 10$ pixels. Note that the plume detection algorithm already estimates a CO₂ or NO₂ background field when the plume is detected by CO₂ or NO₂ observations, respectively. However, since the CO₂ signal-to-noise ratio inside the plume can be close to 1, the CO₂ background calculated with this method may be overestimated. Therefore, we here used the NO₂ observations to flag all pixels potentially affected by the plume to calculate the CO₂ background. The approach was applied to both CO₂ and NO₂ observations to have a consistent method for both trace gases.

In the second step, line densities were computed by integrating the signal in across-plume direction. Line densities were computed for each sub-polygon every 5 km downstream (Figure 2.3) by fitting a Gaussian curve

$$c_p(y) = \frac{q}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \exp\left(-\frac{(y-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (2.2)$$

with plume signal c_p , line density q , shift μ and standard width σ . The plume signal is in units of kg m⁻² converted from ppm or molecules cm⁻², respectively. The line density q has units of kg m⁻¹, i.e. mass of CO₂ or NO₂ within a slice of thickness of 1 m. The CO₂ and NO₂ signals were fitted simultaneously to share the same position (shift) and standard width of the Gaussian curve. Since relative uncertainties are smaller for NO₂ than for CO₂, the NO₂ observations effectively constrain these parameters. Only NO₂ line densities were fitted when no CO₂ observations were available, for example, due to cloud cover. To avoid misfits, the computed flux was used only if at least one observation was available every 5 km in across-plume direction to make sure that the full across-plume values are given by the observations.

To obtain the flux, the wind speed u perpendicular to the centerline is required. This wind speed was computed as the vertically averaged horizontal wind speed at the time of the overpass from COSMO-GHG weighed by the vertical emission profile for combustion in the energy sector (SNAP-1). The emission profiles correspond to the (true) profiles used in the simulations except for Boxberg, Jänschwalde, Lippendorf, Schwarze Pumpe, Turów and Patnów for which plume rise was computed explicitly (Brunner et al., 2019).

For CO₂, the fluxes computed for all individual sub-polygons were averaged to obtain an estimate of the mean source strength. The uncertainty was determined as the standard error of the mean. To obtain NO_x emissions from NO₂ observations, we have to account for NO_x chemistry. For one, the NO_x concentration slowly decays

with time and further there is only a fraction of NO_x available as NO_2 . The NO_x flux therefore depends on plume distance as

$$Q(x) = f \cdot Q_0 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{x}{u \cdot \tau}\right) \quad \text{if } x > 0 \quad (2.3)$$

with NO_2 -to- NO_x conversion factor f , wind speed u , decay time τ , and source strength Q_0 . The conversion factor f was set constant to 1.32 (Beirle et al., 2011). The source strength Q_0 and the decay time τ were obtained by fitting a curve to the individual fluxes $Q(x)$. The decay typically ranges from one to several hours. It was set to a constant value of 4 hours in our simulation. If the number of polygons is insufficient for fitting a NO_x decay time, we estimate NO_x emissions from the two polygons between 0 and 10 km (if available) assuming that no decay occurred over this short distance.

In our simulations, we assumed a constant conversion factor and a constant lifetime, which are strong simplifications. NO_x is emitted from combustion sources primarily in the form of NO but is then partially converted to NO_2 by reaction with ozone. With increasing distance from the source, NO_2 typically becomes the dominant component of NO_x . The partitioning depends on the intensity of solar radiation, temperature, and ozone levels and thus changes not only with distance from the source but also with altitude above surface. In addition, the lifetime of NO_x depends on the concentrations of OH radicals, which themselves depend on multiple factors including the concentrations of NO_2 themselves. Close to NO_x sources, OH levels are depleted due to rapid reaction with NO_2 to HNO_3 . With decreasing NO_2 levels downwind due to dilution and conversion to HNO_3 , OH levels increase thereby reducing NO_x lifetime. As a consequence, $\text{NO}_2:\text{CO}_2$ ratios change with distance from the source and are different under different weather conditions. Such complicating factors need to be accounted for when trying to estimate CO_2 emissions from NO_2 observations, which is appealing since NO_2 can be measured from satellites such as TROPOMI (and in future Sentinel-5) with good accuracy and with much better spatial and temporal coverage compared to the CO_2M mission. However, to fully explore the potential and limitations of this approach, the simple assumption of a constant NO_x lifetime as in our simulations will have to be replaced by full chemistry simulations, which was out of scope of this study.

2.5.1.2 Uncertainties and misfit detection

Several checks have been implemented to avoid misfits and correspondingly wrong emission estimates. The criteria have been chosen such that they can also be applied to real observations. They make it possible to limit the need for visual inspection of the results. The checks are the following:

- Detected plumes are not used when they overlap more than one source.
- Detected plumes are not used when the direction of the center curve and the wind direction disagree by more than ± 45 degrees.
- Detected plumes are not used when the “upstream polygon” contains more than 5 detected plume pixels. This criterion removes cases where the plume overlaps with an upstream source that is outside the swath or covered by clouds.
- Line densities are not computed for polygons that do not have valid satellite observations inside the detected plume every 5 km in across plume direction. The criterion removes misfits when observations near the plume center are missing.
- Line densities are not computed when the polygon is not fully inside the swath.
- Line densities or fitted emissions are not used when the Gaussian curve fit resulted in a large uncertainty.

Uncertainties of the mass-balance approach are caused by instrument noise, uncertainties in wind speed and direction, uncertainties in estimating the background, and a general “methodological uncertainty” (e.g. limits of the plume detection algorithm, assumption of steady-state conditions). The retrieval uncertainty is implicitly accounted for. For wind speed a fixed uncertainty of 2 m s^{-1} was assumed. The methodological and background uncertainty are generally difficult to estimate, but since this is an OSSE study, where true emissions are known, we estimated them from the difference between estimated uncertainty and the standard deviation in the time series of the differences between estimated and true emissions.

2.5.2 Results

2.5.2.1 Plume detection

Figure 2.11 shows examples of detected plumes from CO₂ observations with low noise ($\sigma_{\text{VEG50}} = 0.5$ ppm) and NO₂ observations with high noise ($\sigma_{\text{ref}} = 2 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) on 2 November 2015. The swath is mostly cloud-free and thus the different cloud-filtering thresholds for CO₂ and NO₂ observations are not relevant here. Note that in most cases only a few plumes are actually cloud free and a swath covering a large number of cloud-free and non-overlapping plumes is actually quite rare.

With the NO₂ observations, all nine plumes in the swath can be detected, while only six plumes are detected with the CO₂ observations and the plumes are also smaller. Precision and false positive rate of the plume detection algorithm depend on the parameters used in the algorithm (Eq. 2.1): threshold z_q , systematic error σ_{sys} , width of Gaussian filter used for computing the local mean σ_g , and the size of the neighborhood n_{bg} used for computing the background field. The parameters used here worked well on average. The number of detected pixels could be increased using a lower threshold z_q or a lower systematic error σ_{sys} . However, this would increase the number of overlapping plumes (e.g. Boxberg, Jänschwalde and Schwarze Pumpe) or could cause a whole region to be marked as detected when background variability is very high (e.g. in the northwestern Czech Republic). To increase the number of detectable plumes without increasing the number false positives, spatial and temporal variable parameters are likely necessary for optimal plume detection (see discussions for details).

Figure 2.11: Comparing plume detection using CO₂ observations with low noise ($\sigma_{\text{VEG50}} = 0.5$ ppm) and (b) NO₂ observations with high noise ($\sigma_{\text{ref}} = 2 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$). For each detected plume, the figure shows detected pixels, plume center line and polygons used in the mass-balance approach. The triangular marker shows the location of the source and the wind direction in the model field.

2.5.2.2 Individual CO₂ and NO_x emission estimates

Figure 2.12 shows an example for the application of the mass-balance approach for the coal-fired power plant near Mělník (CZ). The point source has emissions of CO₂ and NO_x of 7.4 Mtyr⁻¹ and 7.2 ktyr⁻¹, respectively, at satellite overpass (10:30 UTC). The example is based on medium-noise CO₂ observations ($\sigma_{\text{VEG50}} = 0.7$ ppm) and high-noise NO₂ observations. The plume was detected from the NO₂ observations (Figure 2.11b). While the plume appears quite isolated in the CO₂ observations (Figure 2.12a), the NO₂ image shows several smaller point sources in the vicinity (Figure 2.12c) that, however, do not overlap with the power plant plume. The center curve was fitted to the 43 satellite pixels of the detected plume. The plume length is 24 km and the width is roughly 10 km. The plume age is about 1.6 hours with an estimated wind speed of 4.2 m s⁻¹ at the

source. The center curve and the wind direction are in good agreement with a discrepancy of only 18 degrees. The plume length of 24 km allows drawing 5 polygons downstream of the source for computing line densities. Figure 2.12c shows CO₂ and NO₂ observations in these five polygons and in the polygon upstream of the source. The computed CO₂ and NO_x fluxes and their uncertainties are shown in Figure 2.12d. Note that only uncertainties in satellite observations and wind speed are included. The CO₂ fluxes are close to zero upstream of the source and then increase to $6.7 \pm 1.7 \text{ Mt yr}^{-1}$ downstream in good agreement with the true emissions of 7.4 Mt yr^{-1} . In contrast to CO₂, the NO_x fluxes decay with distance from the source. The estimated emissions are about 40% larger than the true emissions. The decay time is lower than the true decay time of four hours.

Figure 2.12: Exemplary application of the mass balance approach for the point source near Mělník. (a) CO₂ and (b) NO₂ satellite image with detected plumes and polygons for computing line densities. (c) Across plume CO₂ and NO₂ values for the six polygons with fitted Gaussian curve. (d) CO₂ and NO_x fluxes along the centerline and estimated CO₂ and NO_x emissions.

2.5.2.3 Number of successful CO₂ and NO_x emission estimates

Figure 2.13a shows the number of detected plumes per source from which CO₂ emissions could be estimated successfully. Since plume detection was based on NO₂ observations, the point sources are sorted from the strongest to the weakest source with respect to NO_x emissions. The reference scenario (orange symbols) is based on high-noise NO₂ observations ($\sigma_{\text{ref}} = 2 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) and medium-noise CO₂ observations ($\sigma = 0.7 \text{ ppm}$). For this scenario, the number of successful estimates ranged between 19 and 49 with six satellites. While the number of estimates varies strongly between the sources, no clear trend can be seen when comparing stronger and weaker sources, because other factors like proximity to other sources also affect the number of successful estimates. The number of successful estimates is surprisingly lower when low-noise NO₂ observations ($\sigma_{\text{ref}} = 1 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) are used (blue symbols), because detected plumes are larger and therefore more likely to overlap with neighboring plumes. Furthermore, many point sources are surrounded by weaker sources that can be detected with the low-noise NO₂ observations and are then wrongly assigned to the target source. These situations are typically flagged by the algorithm when the weak sources have pixels in the upstream polygon of the target or when the additional plumes distort the plume shape, which can result in the curve fit to fail or the fitted curve not to be parallel to the wind direction. When CO₂ instead of NO₂ observations are used for plume detection (green and red symbols), the number of successful estimates tends to be smaller because of the lower signal:noise ratio of CO₂ observations. An exception are cases where the detected plumes are smaller and thus less likely to overlap with neighboring plumes (e.g. Boxberg and Lippendorf). Also shown in the figure

are the results for scenarios with NO_x emissions reduced to 30% of today's values, as will be discussed in more detailed later.

Figure 2.13: Number of successful CO_2 emission estimates with 6 satellites for different instrument scenarios (low- and medium-noise CO_2 and low- and high-noise NO_2 observations) and different NO_x emission reduction scenarios applying a scaling of anthropogenic emissions from 0.3 to 1.0. The point sources are sorted from the strongest to the weakest point source with respect to NO_x emissions. The dashed lines are used only for guiding the eye.

For estimating NO_x emissions, the number of successful NO_x estimates ranges from 30 to 77 cases for six satellites (Figure 2.14). NO_2 observations with lower noise can result again in fewer cases. The NO_2 observations always result in more successful NO_x emission estimates, because NO_2 observations can tolerate a higher cloud fraction (30% instead of 1%), which increases the number of cloud-free plumes significantly.

2.5.2.4 Systematic and random uncertainty of individual estimates

The estimated uncertainties of individual CO_2 and NO_x emission estimates can be quite large for a small plume with weak CO_2 and NO_2 signals. Since the number of successful estimates is relatively small and varies strongly between the sources, we quantified the systematic and random uncertainty in several different ways. The median bias (MB) and the standard deviation (SD) were computed from the difference between the estimated and true values. The relative values were computed by dividing by the mean at satellite overpass time (10:30 UTC). Since the differences are not necessarily normally distributed, we computed the 16-84th percentile range (PR) and divided this range by two to be comparable with the standard deviation.

The estimated random uncertainty computed with the mass-balance approach is underestimated (not shown), because it only accounts for uncertainties in the CO_2 and NO_2 observations and in the wind speed but not for uncertainties from, for example, the assumptions of the method and computation of the background field. To quantify the unaccounted uncertainty, median estimated uncertainties were subtracted from the PRs for each source. Figure 2.15 shows this unaccounted uncertainty for CO_2 and NO_x emission estimates as a function of true emissions including a robust linear fit through the individual points. For CO_2 , the intercept is 0.33 Mt yr^{-1} and the slope is 0.34. For NO_x , the intercept is 0.54 Mt yr^{-1} and the slope is 0.28. This suggests that there is an additional relative error of about 30% of the source strength. The non-zero intercept is likely related to an imperfect determination of the background.

The total estimated random uncertainties are shown in Figure 2.16a and b for medium-noise CO_2 ($\sigma_{\text{VEG50}} = 0.7 \text{ ppm}$) and high-noise NO_2 observations ($\sigma_{\text{ref}} = 2 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$). The different measures used for computing random uncertainties for CO_2 and NO_x agree mostly quite well, but, SDs are somewhat larger due to outliers

Figure 2.14: Same as Figure 2.13 but for number of successful NO_x emission estimates.

Figure 2.15: The uncertainty computed with the mass-balance approach (green symbols) is underestimated, because it only accounts for uncertainties in the CO_2 and NO_2 observations and in the wind speed but not for uncertainties from, for example, the assumptions of the method and computation of the background field. This “unaccounted uncertainty” was estimated by comparing the estimated uncertainty with the percentile range of the difference between estimated and true emissions (orange symbols). A robust linear model was fitted to the difference as a function of source strength. For CO_2 , the intercept is 0.33 Mt yr^{-1} and the slope is 0.34. For NO_x , the intercept is 0.54 Mt yr^{-1} and the slope is 0.30. The increased uncertainty including the unaccounted uncertainty is shown as black symbols.

Figure 2.16: Random uncertainty of estimated (a) CO_2 and (b) NO_x emissions as well as (c) $\text{CO}_2:\text{NO}_x$ emission ratios using different measures. Standard deviation and percentile range were computed from the differences between estimated and true emissions. Regression lines were fitted to estimated uncertainties (panel a and b) and percentile ranges (panel c) to obtain slope and intercept.

with large uncertainty. The random uncertainty increases linear with source strength. For CO_2 emissions, the uncertainty is 31% of the source strength plus an offset of 2.0 Mt yr^{-1} . For NO_x emissions, the uncertainty is similarly 29% with a smaller offset of 0.8 kt yr^{-1} .

The CO_2 emissions can be over- or underestimated varying between -34 and +26% (median bias) with a mean of -3%. The NO_x emissions are all overestimated by 26% on average (range: 8 - 48%). The reasons are not entirely clear. One possibility is that the mass-balance estimates include contributions from neighboring plumes not fully removed in the background. The most likely reason is that the assumed constant NO_2 -to- NO_x conversion factor f of 1.32 is a too strong simplification, which is also not compliant with the way NO_x is treated in our simulations. In the simulations, the NO_2 to NO ratio is assumed to depend solely on the total NO_x concentration following Düring et al. (2011). Since the relation is not linear, it can not be applied to total columns. The relative random uncertainty is slightly smaller than for the CO_2 emissions.

2.6 Improved estimation of annual mean emissions and uncertainties

The accuracy of an annual mean estimate derived from individual overpasses on a small number of days depends critically on how well the temporal variability of emissions is captured and how well we can fill the gaps in time not covered by the observations. In this study, the COSMO-GHG simulations used hourly emission fields as input, which were derived from annual emissions using diurnal, weekly and seasonal time profiles based on the Selected Nomenclature for Air Pollution (SNAP) categories (Pouliot et al., 2012; Jähn et al., 2020). However, real hour-to-hour and day-to-day variability is expected to be higher (e.g. Nassar et al., 2013; Super et al., 2020b).

In this task, we therefore improved the estimated annual mean emissions and their uncertainties by considering the temporal variability of emissions. Annual emissions were obtained by fitting a low order C-spline to the individual estimates for different constellations. We used periodic boundary conditions to smoothly connect the end and the beginning of the year. The fitted curve is then integrated to obtain annual emissions. Their uncertainties are estimated by error propagation from the random uncertainties of the individual estimates.

The low-order spline accounts for a seasonal cycle varying slowly with time but does not account for more rapid day-to-day variability. Since CO2M is in a sun-synchronous orbit with fixed overpass time, individual estimates are only representative of emissions a few hours before the satellite overpass but not for the daily mean (Broquet et al., 2018). It is therefore necessary to apply a correction factor correcting for the mid-day sampling bias to obtain the annual mean emissions, which introduces an additional source of uncertainty. We assume here that a mean diurnal cycle can be obtained from bottom-up inventories or other observations (e.g., ground-based monitoring networks or geostationary satellites), while deviations from such a mean behavior need to be accounted for in the uncertainty budget.

2.6.1 Results for power plant emissions

2.6.1.1 Uncertainty of temporal variability

The time profiles prescribed for combustion plants (SNAP-1) are shown in Figure 2.17. At satellite overpass, both CO₂ and NO_x emissions are about 20% higher than the daily mean. The weekly cycle has a reduction by about 20% on weekends and the seasonal emissions are about 20% higher than the annual mean in winter and about 20% lower in summer. These time profiles are not necessarily representative for large power plants (especially lignite powered plants) that operate for baseload, while power plants designed for peak power might have much stronger and less predictable variability. We therefore do not apply any sampling bias correction factor but compare with the emissions at satellite overpass. Since our results (e.g., detection threshold and uncertainties) depend strongly on the emission strength at overpass, this makes it easier to generalize our results in case diurnal cycles are different.

Figure 2.17: Normalized (a) diurnal, (b) weekly and (c) seasonal cycle of emissions used in simulations.

Hill and Nassar (2019) analyzed the hour-to-hour and day-to-day variability of emissions for the 50 largest power plants in the United States. They found that after subtracting a mean seasonal and diurnal cycle, the remaining hour-to-hour and day-to-day variabilities were 28.7% and 31.0%, respectively. We use these values to estimate the uncertainty associated with the temporal variability. Since these variations were computed after subtracting a mean diurnal and seasonal cycle, we implicitly assume that a mean cycle can be obtained

accurately. To compute the overall relative uncertainty σ_Q , we assume that the errors are independent and reduce with the number of successful estimates n :

$$\sigma_Q = \sqrt{s_Q^2 + \frac{s_d^2}{n} + \frac{s_h^2}{n}} \quad (2.4)$$

where s_Q is the estimated (relative) uncertainty obtained from integrating the seasonal cycle, s_d the day-to-day and s_h the hour-to-hour uncertainty.

2.6.1.2 Time series of estimated emissions

As an example, Figure 2.18 shows the time series of estimated CO₂ and NO_x emission for Jänschwalde and Mělník for a constellation of three satellites using medium-noise CO₂ ($\sigma_{\text{VEG50}} = 0.7$ ppm) and high-noise NO₂ observations ($\sigma_{\text{ref}} = 2 \times 10^{15}$ cm⁻²). The black lines show the true emissions at satellite overpass time (10:30 UTC). The weekly and seasonal cycle is clearly visible in the true emissions.

Figure 2.18: Time series of estimated CO₂ and NO_x emissions and CO₂:NO_x emission ratios at (a) Jänschwalde and (b) Mělník for a constellation of three satellites using medium-noise CO₂ ($\sigma_{\text{VEG50}} = 0.7$ ppm) and NO₂ observations ($\sigma_{\text{ref}} = 2 \times 10^{15}$ cm⁻²).

At Jänschwalde, 13 and 24 successful CO₂ and NO_x estimates are available with a large spread from 2 to 7 CO₂ estimates for individual satellites. At Mělník, the numbers are 17 and 23 successful CO₂ and NO_x estimates, respectively. For both point sources, temporal coverage is low in winter due to frequent cloud cover.

As mentioned above, the annual mean emissions were computed by integrating the C-spline fitted to the individual estimates. At Mělník, the shape of the seasonal cycle is fitted well. The annual CO₂ and NO_x emissions are estimated to 6.4 ± 1.7 Mt yr⁻¹ and 7.1 ± 1.2 kt yr⁻¹ agreeing with the true emissions within the estimated uncertainties. At Jänschwalde, the lack of estimates in winter results in an overestimation in winter, but again the annual mean emissions agree with the true emissions within the estimated uncertainties.

2.6.1.3 Annual emissions

Figure 2.19 compares annual mean estimates obtained for all 15 power plants with true annual emissions at satellite overpass (10:30 UTC) using medium-noise CO₂ ($\sigma_{\text{VEG50}} = 0.7$ ppm) and high-noise NO₂ observations ($\sigma_{\text{ref}} = 2 \times 10^{15}$ cm⁻²). The small markers show the individual results for the 20 different constellations of three

satellites that could be constructed from the six simulated satellites (a-f). The large marker shows the median of all 20 combinations and its estimated uncertainty. Regression lines were fitted for the median and for the individual constellations.

Figure 2.19: Annual estimates of (a) CO_2 and (b) NO_x emissions and (c) emission ratios for a constellation of three satellites for the 15 largest point sources in the model domain using medium-noise CO_2 ($\sigma_{\text{VEG50}} = 0.7$ ppm) and high-noise NO_2 observations ($\sigma_{\text{ref}} = 2 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$). In addition, CO_2 emissions were obtained from (d) the annual NO_x emissions using an estimated emissions ratio R_e and (e) the true emission ratio R_t used in the simulations. Large markers show the median constellation and small markers the 20 possible combinations of 3 satellites that could be constructed as permutations of the six simulated satellites. Regression lines were fitted to the median as well as to the individual constellations. Slope, intercept and Pearson correlation coefficient r^2 are displayed for the median and for the range of the 20 constellations. True emissions correspond to emissions at satellite overpass at 10:30 UTC.

The CO_2 emissions correlate quite well with the true emissions with a Pearson correlation coefficient (r^2) ranging from 0.87 to 0.98, a slope ranging from 0.92 to 1.21, and an intercept slightly larger than zero (Figure 2.19a). NO_x emissions correlate even better with r^2 ranging from 0.97 to 0.98, but emissions are slightly overestimated (Figure 2.19b).

Figure 2.20 shows the estimated uncertainty of annual CO_2 and NO_x emissions for the 15 power plants for a constellation of either two or three CO_2M satellites. The markers denote the median uncertainties and the bars the range obtained for the individual constellations. The uncertainties were computed by error propagation following Eq. 2.4. The overall uncertainty is thus driven by the precision of the individual estimates and the number of successful estimates.

In general, the uncertainty is proportional to the source strength Q and can be described by a regression line with slope m and intercept b . For CO_2 , the uncertainty has a slope of 21% and an intercept of 1.1 Mt yr^{-1} for two satellites with no large differences for different NO_x scaling factors (Figure 2.20a). This suggests that the plumes could be detected well from the NO_2 observations even if NO_x emissions were reduced significantly in

Figure 2.20: Estimated uncertainty of annual mean of emissions of (a) CO_2 in Mt yr^{-1} and (b) NO_x in kt yr^{-1} for a constellation of two CO_2M satellites. Uncertainties are also shown for CO_2 estimates using NO_x estimates and (c) estimated and (d) true $\text{CO}_2:\text{NO}_x$ emission ratios. (e-h) shows the same but for a constellation of three CO_2M satellites.

the future with improved cleaning technology. The contribution of uncertainty in the temporal variability is roughly a third of the total uncertainty. The uncertainty of NO_x emissions has a similar dependency on true emissions (Figure 2.20b), but tends to be smaller than for CO_2 ($m = 0.18$ and $b = 0.3 \text{ kt yr}^{-1}$).

The median uncertainties are only slightly smaller for three satellites than for two, but the range between individual constellations is much smaller. A constellation of three satellites is thus less likely to produce highly uncertain results due to insufficient coverage than a constellation of two.

Figure 2.21a shows the number of annual CO_2 emission estimates with a given uncertainty threshold for point sources with CO_2 emissions between 9-11 Mt yr^{-1} , i.e. Pocerady, Turow, Schwarze Pumpe, and Dolna Odra (see Table 2.1). The numbers were computed considering all possible constellations of two or three satellites. Separate lines are shown for the different NO_x scaling factors, which affect the detectability of the plumes. A constellation of three satellites would be able to quantify annual CO_2 emissions in about 80-95% of cases with an uncertainty of 30% or better. A constellation of two satellites could only quantify less than 70% of point

Figure 2.21: Number of successful (a) CO_2 and (b) NO_x estimates for a given uncertainty threshold considering constellations of two or three satellites and different NO_x scaling factors. For CO_2 , point sources with source strengths from 9 to 11 Mt yr^{-1} were considered while for NO_x , sources with 4-6 and 9-11 kt yr^{-1} were considered.

sources with similar accuracy.

In terms of annual NO_x emissions, two and three satellites could quantify nearly 100% of point sources with emissions of the order of 10 kt yr^{-1} with an uncertainty of 30%. For a smaller source of the order of 5 kt yr^{-1} , the numbers would reduce to 70 and 95%, respectively.

2.6.1.4 Global application of the mass-balance approach

The mass-balance approach can be applied globally, because it does not require any additional expensive atmospheric transport simulations, but solely relies on wind information that is available from global analysis and reanalysis products. A database of points sources is available through the global map of emissions clumps (Wang et al., 2019), which lists about 900 point sources with CO_2 emissions larger than 3.5 Mt yr^{-1} at CO2M overpass time (Figure 2.22a). We use a threshold of 3.5 Mt yr^{-1} here, because it is close to the weakest source in our study (Table 2.1).

Figure 2.22: (a) Distribution of point sources based on CO_2 emissions at satellite overpass (11:30 local time) from Wang et al. (2019). (b) Estimated uncertainty of annual emissions for point sources $>3.5 \text{ Mt yr}^{-1}$ for a constellation of two or three CO2M satellites. (c) Number of point sources that can be quantified with an uncertainty below given threshold with two or three CO2M satellites.

To upscale our results, we use the regression lines found for the uncertainties of annual emissions (Figure 2.20a and e) to calculate uncertainties for all point sources. We expect that our results are representative for the sources in the database, because about 90% of them are located in the mid-latitudes ($23.4^\circ - 66.5^\circ$) like our study area ($50^\circ \text{ N} - 55^\circ \text{ N}$) and thus have a similar number of satellite overpasses ranging from 1.1 to 2.7 per 11-day repeat cycle compared to 1.7 in our study area.

Figure 2.22b shows the uncertainties of annual emissions computed for the 900 point sources for a constellation of two and three satellites showing that adding a third satellite reduces uncertainties from 35 to 28% on average. As a result, two satellites would be able to quantify annual emissions with an uncertainty $<30\%$ for only 300 point sources, while three satellites could quantify emissions for 600 point sources (Figure 2.22c). The 300 and 600 sources account for total emissions of 6000 Mt yr^{-1} and 8700 Mt yr^{-1} , which are about 16% and 24% of global anthropogenic emissions.

Therefore, adding a third CO2M satellite has the potential to double the number of quantifiable point sources. Since our analysis used the regression lines in Figure 2.20, the numbers are likely overestimated, because some point sources are insufficiently covered by the satellites (Figure 2.21). However, this would especially affect a constellation of two satellites making it likely that we still underestimate the benefit of a third satellite here.

2.6.2 Results for city emissions

Annual emissions of cities were also quantified by fitting a C-spline (Section 2.4 and Kuhlmann et al. (2020a)). However, the quantification of the sampling bias and its uncertainty is more difficult than for power plants, because a city consists of a large number of different sources from different sectors each having different temporal variabilities. As different cities have different sector mixes, time profiles will be different for different cities.

Figure 2.23: Time profiles for (a) diurnal, (b) weekly and (c) seasonal cycles of CO_2 and NO_x emissions and $\text{CO}_2:\text{NO}_x$ emission ratios for Berlin as assumed in the SMARTCARB simulations.

In our simulation, Berlin’s emissions during overpass are about 18% higher than the daily mean, suggesting that the sampling bias introduced by an 11:30 LT overpass time would be of the same order of magnitude. However, this result is entirely driven by the sector-specific diurnal emission cycles prescribed in the simulations (Figure 2.23). If the diurnal cycle of emissions was well known, this sampling bias could be corrected for. The diurnal (and weekly and seasonal) cycles used in our simulations are widely applied in the air pollution (and GHG) modelling community. However, the uncertainty in these profiles is very poorly known, which makes it difficult to estimate the uncertainty that would be introduced by a sampling bias correction. Studies such as those of Nassar et al. (2013), Gurney et al. (2019), or Peylin et al. (2011) all present diurnal emission cycles from various sources of information, but no analysis of uncertainties. The diurnal cycles presented in these studies are roughly in line with our estimate of a sampling bias of the order of 20% with respect to the daily mean. Super et al. (2020a) estimated uncertainties in the diurnal variation from uncertainties in activity data and emission factors, which, when applied to individual cities, would make it possible to better quantify the potential sampling bias in the future. Because much more work is needed to better quantify diurnal variability and the associated uncertainties (including temporal correlations in these uncertainties), we did not correct for the temporal sampling bias of city emissions in this study.

2.7 Quantitative usage of NO₂ for CO₂ source estimation

2.7.1 Quantitative usage of NO_x emission estimates for point sources

2.7.1.1 Method

Since NO₂ observations will be available from the CO2M mission with much higher accuracy and better temporal coverage due to the lower sensitivity to clouds, it is appealing to use NO_x emission estimates quantitatively to estimate CO₂ emissions. We tested this idea by deriving CO₂ emissions directly from satellite NO₂ measurements and applying a constant CO₂:NO_x emission ratio computed from those overpasses, where both CO₂ and NO_x emissions could be estimated reliably (Task 2.5). Since ratios are very sensitive to outliers, especially when NO_x estimates are close to zero, we filter the time series for outliers that are more than 1.5× outside the interquartile range (25th - 75th percentile).

The emission ratio is used to convert the estimated annual NO_x emissions to CO₂ emissions. The uncertainty of the emission ratio is computed from the scatter of the individual estimates. Annual mean ratios were used here, because individual estimates are too uncertain for estimating CO₂ emissions from NO_x emissions. For comparison, we also compute CO₂ emissions from NO_x estimates using the true emission ratio taken from the bottom-up inventory.

2.7.1.2 Results

The number of individual estimates of CO₂:NO_x emission ratios is equal to or smaller than the number of CO₂ estimates, because in rare cases NO_x emissions could not be estimated (when the decay time could not be estimated reliably). The emission ratios are underestimated because NO_x emissions were overestimated. Figure 2.16c shows the uncertainty of the individual CO₂:NO_x emission ratios for the fifteen power plant sources. The relative precision is about 50% for SD and PR. A major challenge is that the uncertainty of the CO₂:NO_x emission ratios cannot be obtained by standard error propagation relying on Gaussian errors, because the distribution of the ratios is heavy-tailed. We therefore estimate the uncertainty from repeated random sampling of the ratio using the estimated CO₂ and NO_x uncertainties and determine the precision as half the 16-84th percentile range of the distribution. The estimated uncertainty is significantly larger than SD and PR, because we assumed that the CO₂ and NO_x uncertainties are independent, which is not the case, because they use both, for example, the same wind speed.

As an example, Figure 2.18 shows the time series of emission ratios for Mělník and Jäschwalde after filtering out all outliers using medium-noise CO₂ ($\sigma_{\text{VEG50}} = 0.7$ ppm) and high-noise NO₂ observations ($\sigma_{\text{ref}} = 2 \times 10^{15}$ cm⁻²). The ratios were estimated as 816 ± 271 (33%) for Mělník and 973 ± 104 (11%) for Jäschwalde. Since CO₂ and NO_x emissions from power plants have the same time profiles, the CO₂:NO_x emission ratios do not depend on time in our simulations. However, since the true emissions were computed as the sum of all emissions in the 1 km × 1 km cell of the model grid, which may include emissions from other sectors with different CO₂:NO_x ratios, the ratios may show a weak temporal variability. This is true for the relatively weak point source at Mělník, whereas the strong point source at Jäschwalde has no time-dependent emission ratios. Figure 2.19c compares the estimated annual mean ratios with the true emission ratios. The correlation r^2 between estimated and true emission ratios is quite low ranging from 0.22 to 0.74. The ratios were underestimated due to overestimated NO_x emissions.

Figure 2.19d and e compare CO₂ emissions estimated from NO_x emissions using either the estimated emission ratio R_e or the true ratio R_t . When the estimated ratios are used, correlation is high with r^2 ranging from 0.94 to 0.98 and a slope ranging from 0.93 to 1.10. Since NO_x emissions were overestimated and ratios were underestimated, estimated CO₂ emissions have only a small bias. When using the true emission ratio, the positive bias of the NO_x emissions carries over to the CO₂ emissions resulting in an overestimation of the CO₂ emissions. The correlation coefficient, on the other hand, is higher with r^2 of 0.99, because NO_x emissions were estimated with higher accuracy than CO₂ emissions due to the higher precision of individual estimates and the larger number of successful estimates.

Figure 2.20 shows the uncertainties of CO₂ emissions estimated from NO_x emissions using the estimated and true emission ratio. When CO₂ emissions are quantified using NO_x emissions and the estimated CO₂:NO_x

emission ratio (Figure 2.20c and g), the relative uncertainty is similar to, or larger than, the uncertainty computed for CO₂ emissions, because of the high uncertainties of the estimated emission ratios. The uncertainty increases for smaller scaling factors, because the uncertainty of weaker NO_x is higher. If the true emission ratio would be known, CO₂ emission could be estimated from NO_x emissions with lower uncertainty but only when NO_x emissions are not reduced drastically.

2.7.2 Quantitative usage of NO_x emission estimates for cities

The same method can also be applied to the emissions of Berlin. Since a city is not a point source, NO₂ line densities build up slowly over the city and then decay downstream due to the limited lifetime of NO_x. We follow the approach proposed by Beirle et al. (2011) to describe the flux Q up- and downstream of the source:

$$Q(x) = fQ_0 \cdot (D(x) * G(x)) \quad (2.5)$$

where f is the NO₂ to NO_x conversion factor, Q_0 is the source strength, D is the decay function and G is a Gaussian function that describes the spatial extent of the city. The NO₂ decay function is

$$D(x) = \begin{cases} \exp\left(-\frac{(x-x_{\text{source}})}{x_0}\right) & \text{if } x \geq x_{\text{source}} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2.6)$$

with source location x_{source} and decay length x_0 . The decay length is the product of wind speed and decay time τ . To obtain NO_x emissions, we fit source strength Q_0 and decay time τ to Equation (2.5) using fluxes computed up- and downstream of the source.

Figure 2.24: Example of estimated (a) CO₂ and (b) NO_x emissions using the mass-balance approach applied to the city plume of Berlin.

Figure 2.24 shows an example of estimated CO₂ and NO_x emissions for Berlin showing that NO_x emissions can be estimated with higher precision from CO₂M observations than CO₂ emissions. This suggests that if the CO₂:NO_x emission ratio is known with sufficient accuracy, CO₂ emissions could be deduced from estimated NO_x emissions with higher precision. The challenge for cities is that total emissions are the sum of different emission sectors. Each sector has different time profiles and emission ratios. As a result, emission ratios vary strongly with time. Figure 2.23 shows the diurnal, weekly and seasonal cycles of CO₂ and NO_x emissions assumed in the SMARTCARB simulations. The resulting CO₂:NO_x emission ratios have very strong temporal variability. For example, the seasonal cycle ranges from 700 to 1300. This adds an additional source of uncertainty to the estimated ratios making quantitative usage of NO_x emission estimates likely not feasible with emission ratios estimated from CO₂M observations alone.

2.8 Consideration of expected future reduction in NO₂ emissions from power plants

2.8.1 NO_x reduction scenarios

The CO₂ and NO_x emissions used in this study are based on the TNO/MACC-3 inventory for the year 2015. Since 2017 a new EU regulation is in effect that requires a significant reduction of NO_x emissions for large combustion plants (European Commission, 2017, Table 3). For large lignite-fuelled power plants, the regulation requires new plants built after ratification of the regulation to reduce NO_x concentrations in the flue gas to 50-85 mg m⁻³. Existing power plants need to reduce flue gas concentrations to <85-150 mg m⁻³ by 2021. NO_x concentrations of up to 200 mg m⁻³ were allowed prior to the new regulation.

Based on reported NO_x flue gas concentrations for German power plants (Tebert, 2017), we expect that NO_x emissions used in our simulations will be reduced by 20% to 50% for existing plants. Power plants built after 2017 would have NO_x emissions that are about a third of the levels assumed in our simulations. To study the influence of a future reduction of NO_x emissions on our results, we scale anthropogenic NO_x fields in the simulations with factors of 0.3, 0.5 and 0.8. Note that power plants built after 2017 are obviously not present in our simulation for 2015.

Since CO₂ emissions are not affected by these regulations, CO₂:NO_x emission ratios will increase in the future. Table 2.1 shows that emission ratios (on a mass per mass basis) for German power plants are about 1200 in the TNO/MACC-3 inventory for 2015. The emission ratios for power plants in the Czech Republic (CZ) and Poland (PL) are lower, which means that even stronger NO_x reductions will likely be required to fulfil the new regulation. Table 2.3 shows emission ratios for 2015 and 2017 based on self-reported emissions published in the E-PRTR database in 2019. For many power plants higher emission ratios are reported for 2017 compared to 2015 and also compared to ratios used in our study (Table 2.1), likely because operators already implemented procedures to reduce NO_x emissions that are not yet considered in the TNO/MACC-3 inventory. Emissions of point sources in the TNO/MACC-3 inventory can also deviate from the E-PRTR database, because emissions were scaled to resolve discrepancies between national totals and the totals of all individual sources (H. Denier von der Gon, personal communication).

Table 2.3: Emission ratios comparing 2015 and 2017 based on data published in the E-PRTR database (last access: 27 July 2020)

Point source	2015	2017
Jänschwalde	1238	1263
Boxberg	1444	1415
Lippendorf	1286	1369
Prunéřov	767	1272
Počerady	774	1022
Turów	1061	1436
Schwarze Pumpe	2117	2021
Dolna Odra	982	954
Opole	1007	1402
Mělník	783	802
Heyden	1500	1478
Staudinger	1503	1512
Chvaletice	779	1059

2.8.2 Impact of emission reduction

When anthropogenic NO_x emissions are reduced, the number of plumes with successful CO₂ estimates increases slightly for the strongest points sources (Figure 2.13b), because the plumes are shorter and thus less likely to overlap with neighboring plumes. The number of successful estimates does not change compared to the reference

case except for weak point sources for the case with strongest NO_x emission reduction, i.e. where a scaling of 0.3 was applied and NO_x emissions would be smaller than $2 \text{ kt NO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$. Note that there is no clear threshold in terms of source strength, because the successful estimation also depends on other factors such as isolation of the plume and typical wind speeds.

A reduction of NO_x emissions with unchanged CO_2 emissions could result in CO_2 being better suited for plume detection than NO_2 observations. However, Figures 2.13c and d show that even for strongest NO_x reduction, the NO_2 observations outperform CO_2 observations for plume detection in most cases. Only for Staudinger and Chvalteice, CO_2 observations are better than high-noise NO_2 observations, but they are not better than low-noise NO_2 observations.

The number of successful NO_x estimates only changes strongly with the strongest reduction of NO_x emissions in case of the the weakest sources (Figure 2.14c). For these cases NO_2 observations with lower noise would be desirable (Figure 2.14d).

Figure 2.25 compares MB and PR where successful estimates were available for all four scaling factors. For CO_2 estimates, we found no clear dependency on scaling factor in most cases. For NO_x estimates, the PR range increase with reduced NO_x fields but this also corresponds to lower NO_x emissions and absolute PRs actually slightly reduce for lower emissions. For weaker sources, the range of uncertainty can be quite large especially when anthropogenic NO_x fields are scaled by 0.3. Note that true emissions change for the four different scaling factors and that all NO_x emissions are smaller than 10 kt yr^{-1} with a scaling factor of 0.3.

Figure 2.25: Relative median bias (MB) and percentile range (PR) of estimated (a) CO_2 and (b) NO_x emissions, and (c) $\text{CO}_2\text{:NO}_x$ emission ratios for different NO_x scaling factors.

When CO_2 emissions are quantified using NO_x emissions and the estimated $\text{CO}_2\text{:NO}_x$ emission ratio (Figure 2.20c and g), the uncertainty is similar or larger than the uncertainty computed for CO_2 emissions because of the high uncertainty of the estimated emission ratios. The uncertainties tend to increase when NO_x emissions are reduced. If the true emission ratio would be known, CO_2 emission could be estimated from NO_x emissions with higher precision but only when NO_x emissions are not reduced drastically.

Figure 2.21a shows that a drastic reduction of NO_x emissions (scaling factor: 0.3) would reduce the number of estimates with 30% precision especially with two satellites.

For NO_x , we do not distinguish between different scaling factors. To quantify NO_x emissions with a precision of 30% or better, two and three satellites could quantify nearly 100% of point sources with emissions about 10 kt yr^{-1} . Note, however, that with a scaling factor of 0.5, only Janschwalde and Boxberg have emissions around 10 kt yr^{-1} .

3. Work package 2: Evaluation of plume simulations

3.1 Objectives of the work package

The main objective of work package 2 is to conduct and analyse additional and previous COSMO-GHG simulations in order to investigate the realism of the simulated power plant and city plumes. Furthermore, the impact of transport uncertainties, as assessed by varying model settings, on emission estimates is evaluated. The work package included the following tasks:

Task 1: Identification of suitable case studies Identify suitable case studies by considering a) availability of observations for model evaluation, b) availability of simulations from other models, c) sufficiently cloud-free scenes, d) magnitude of the simulated/observed plumes.

Task 2: Sensitivity to model settings For a subset of the selected cases, study the sensitivity of the structure of individual plumes to specific model settings, potentially including advection scheme, turbulence scheme, horizontal numerical diffusion, and emission profiles.

Task 3: Compare with observations and other model simulations For the selected cases, evaluate the representation of power plant and city plumes in COSMO-GHG against observations and other model simulations.

Task 4: Impact of transport uncertainties on emission estimates Apply plume detection algorithm to the same plumes simulated by different models (or model settings) and assess spread in estimated CO₂ emissions. Assess contribution to model spread caused by differences in wind speed, plume dispersion and plume direction.

In order to address these tasks, the report for this work package has been structured as follows: In Section 3.2 the performance of COSMO-GHG is evaluated against observations of power plant and city plumes. Observations include airborne in-situ and remote sensing observations of CO₂ (power plants) and NO₂ (city) with a strong focus on power plant plumes, since these more isolated plumes offer a more robust comparison target. In Section 3.3 we examine the influence of different model settings on the transport simulations discussed in Section 3.2. A systematic analysis of comparison statistics is conducted in order to deduce most favourable settings for GHG simulations with COSMO. Finally, Section 3.4 discusses the impact of model transport uncertainty, as assessed through model runs with different model settings, on emission estimation applying the plume detection and emission quantification algorithm developed in work package 1.

3.2 Evaluation of selected COSMO-GHG plume simulations against real world observations

During the first phase of the SMARTCARB project the potential of quantifying CO₂ emissions from cities and power plants from a constellation of CO₂M satellites was investigated based on a whole year of 'nature runs' of the atmospheric transport model COSMO-GHG at 1 km x 1 km resolution. These model fields were combined with satellite orbit simulations and instrument noise scenarios to generate synthetic observations for constellations of up to six CO₂ satellites optionally measuring also NO₂ and/or CO. Here, in the second phase of the project, the realism of the simulated city and power plant plumes was analysed by comparison to observations. Results of this comparison are discussed in the present chapter, whereas the impact of selecting different model setups is presented in chapter 3.3.

3.2.1 Selected measurement campaigns and model setup

In the following, a brief description of the observational data that was selected for the model comparison is given. These observations were considered the most suitable for achieving the aim of the project.

3.2.1.1 Power plant plumes

Unique airborne observations of power plant plumes were conducted during the Carbon Dioxide and Methane Mission (CoMet, Fix et al., 2018; Fiehn et al., 2020) campaign including several dedicated aircraft overflights of the Bełchatów (Poland) and Jaenschwalde (Germany) power stations. Both in-situ and remote sensing instrumentation were carried by three different aircraft targeting each power plant on one day in spring 2018 (details see Table 3.1).

Table 3.1: Overview of aircraft flights sampling power plant plumes. Times refer to period over target area not whole flight duration. MAMAP and CHARM-F are remote sensing instruments, CRDS and QCLS measure in-situ.

Power plant	Aircraft	Instrumentation	Date	Start (UTC)	End (UTC)
BEL	DLR Cessna	QCLS, meteo	2018-06-07	13:16	15:02
BEL	DLR Halo	CRDS, meteo	2018-06-07	13:42	13:56
BEL	FUB Cessna	MAMAP	2018-06-07	12:29	13:27
BEL	FUB Cessna	MAMAP	2018-06-07	13:50	14:45
BEL	DLR Halo	CHARM-F, meteo	2018-06-07	13:06	13:30
JAE	FUB Cessna	QCLS	2018-05-23	10:06	10:49
JAE	FUB Cessna	MAMAP	2018-05-23	09:00	09:47
JAE	DLR Halo	CHARM-F, meteo	2018-05-23	08:28	09:31

In-situ observations of the Bełchatów power plant plume, including a Quantum Cascade Laser Spectrometer (QCLS) for GHGs and basic meteorological instrumentation, were conducted on board a Cessna aircraft operated by DLR (DLR Cessna). The DLR Halo aircraft carried both in-situ (Cavity Ring Down Spectrometer (CRDS) for GHGs, basic meteorology) and active remote sensing instrumentation (CHARM-F lidar for CO₂ and CH₄, Amediek et al., 2017). Although the DLR Halo flights mainly focused on total column measurements, two transects at plume height were performed at the Bełchatów power plant. An additional Cessna aircraft operated by the Freie Universität Berlin (FUB Cessna) carried the Methane Airborne Mapper (MAMAP) instrument. MAMAP is a passive remote sensing spectrometer measuring in the short wave infrared, which was designed to retrieve total columns of CH₄ and CO₂ below the cruise altitude of the platform carrying the instrument (Gerilowski et al., 2011; Krings et al., 2011). MAMAP was developed by the University of Bremen and the Helmholtz Centre Potsdam, GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences. Total columns are retrieved using the WFM-DOAS algorithm, which does not utilise prior knowledge of the target compounds concentration (Krings et al., 2011). The instrument was successfully deployed previously for the quantification

of large point sources of CH₄ and CO₂ (Klings et al., 2018, e.g.,). During the Jaenschwalde overflights, the FUB Cessna, in addition to remote sensing MAMAP observations, conducted in-situ observations of CO₂ as part of a dedicated curtain flight.

All flights targeted the power plant plumes at distances from below 1 km to about 30 km from the source, with a focus of remote sensing closer to the source and in-situ observations at mid-range.

3.2.1.2 City plumes

In order to take advantage of the simulations already conducted in the first phase of the SMARTCARB project, the plume of the city of Berlin was analyzed and two days (11 August and 29 September 2015) were selected, for which airborne observations of NO₂ from the airborne spectrometer AirMAP of the University of Bremen (Schönhardt et al., 2015) are available, recorded as part of the AROMAT-2 campaign (Andreas Carlos, 2018). No observations of CO₂ are available for these plumes, but the evaluation of the simulated NO₂ should provide similar insights into the ability of the model to represent such plumes as would an evaluation of CO₂.

3.2.1.3 COSMO-GHG simulations

Dedicated model simulations for the comparison against observations at power plants were conducted with COSMO-GHG version 5.6a (Jähn et al., 2020) making use of the recently implemented online emissions modules (anthropogenic and biogenic). Comparisons of city plumes were conducted against previous COSMO-GHG simulations as used within SMARTCARB phase 1 (Kuhlmann et al., 2019a).

3.2.1.4 COSMO-GHG control run

COSMO was run for a domain spanning Eastern Germany and Western Poland (including both the Bełchatów and the Jaenschwalde power stations) at a horizontal resolution of 0.01°x 0.01 ° (~1.1 km) and on 60 vertical levels.

Meteorological initial and boundary conditions were obtained from hourly analysis fields of the operational COSMO-7 configuration run by MeteoSwiss at ~7 km x 7 km horizontal resolution. The simulations made use of COSMO's observation nudging capability for meteorological variables (wind speed and direction, pressure, temperature) as observed at surface synoptic stations and from radio soundings.

The COSMO-GHG simulations distinguished several different CO₂ tracers. Anthropogenic CO₂ was split into three tracers representing i) emissions from the specific power plant under investigation, ii) all other emissions from the power production sector (GNFR A), and iii) all remaining anthropogenic sources. The annual average anthropogenic emissions of CO₂ were taken from the TNO-GHGco inventory (Super et al., 2020b) for the year 2015 and were available for 12 different GNFR categories. Temporal (month of year, time of day, day of week) and vertical emission profiles as described in Jähn et al. (2020) were applied to each GNFR category as part of the online emission module of COSMO-GHG. Tracer advection was solved using Bott's positive-definite 2nd order finite-volume method with Strang-splitting (Bott, 1989).

Average annual point source emissions of the two analysed power plants were updated from E-PRTR ¹ for the year 2017 and the location of the emissions within the TNO inventory was checked against actual stack locations. The latter led to a correction of the emission location by one grid cell (1 km). Such location mismatches most likely result from point source emissions being reported for the street address of the facility and not at actual stack locations. For large facilities, like coal fired power stations, this can lead to similar mismatches and should be considered when high-resolution simulation are conducted.

Biogenic CO₂ was treated by two separate tracers representing gross photosynthetic production and respiration, respectively. Biogenic fluxes were calculated online following the Vegetation Photosynthesis and Respiration Model (VPRM) approach (Mahadevan et al., 2008). A separate CO₂ tracer was reserved for the advection of boundary concentrations. These and their initial distribution were taken from ECMWF CAMS global model (experiment gznv) available 3-hourly at a horizontal resolution of 0.1°x 0.1°.

¹<https://prtr.eea.europa.eu/> last accessed 2020-08-30

Simulations were initialised at midnight the day before the specific plume observations took place, allowing for a spin-up period of at least 32 hours (earliest observations at 8 UTC on second day of simulation). CO₂ tracers with emissions within the model domain were initialised with zero concentrations. Three-dimensional model output was stored at 15 minute resolution (instantaneous values not averages) allowing for a detailed analysis of the dynamic changes in the emerging power plant plumes.

3.2.1.5 Power plant emissions and release height

The average annual emissions of the Bełchatów power station were 37.1 Tg of CO₂ for the year 2017 (E-PRTR). Considering the annual emission cycle, actual simulated emissions at the time of observation were slightly lower, 36.8 Tg yr⁻¹. At the site emissions are released through two 300 m tall stacks, which are located at a horizontal distance of ~300 m. We chose the midpoint of these two stacks as the release location for the present simulations (19.3267°E, 51.2659°N).

The average annual emissions of the Jaenschwalde power station were 23.6 Tg of CO₂ for the year 2017 (E-PRTR) and simulated emissions at the time of observation were 24.8 Tg yr⁻¹. After running through different stages of flue gas treatment the exhausts from the power station are finally released through the 100 m tall cooling towers of the plant. Only the six southernmost of the nine cooling towers in Jaenschwalde are used in this way. We chose the central point of these six towers as the release location for the present simulations (14.4582° E, 51.8365° N).

Figure 3.1: Time series of calculated effective release height for the Blechatow (top) and Jaenschwalde (bottom) power plants.

Table 3.2: Mean effective release height, h_e , and standard width of the Gaussian distribution, σ_{h_e} , for the different power plant CO₂ tracers. Note that the default GNFR-A profile, which was applied for tracers BELA and JAEA, does not follow a Gaussian distribution but is skewed to larger heights.

Site	Tracer	h_e (m)	σ_{h_e} (m)
BEL	BELA	356	non Gaussian
	BELB	620	150
	BELC	830	120
JAE	JAEA	356	non Gaussian
	JAEB	300	120
	JAEC	600	120

For both power plants three tracers with different vertical emission profiles were simulated. The first power plant tracer followed our default GNFR-A vertical emission profile applied for the energy production sector (Brunner et al., 2019) (BELA and JAEA in the following). The release profiles for the two additional tracers were calculated using a plume rise algorithm as detailed in Brunner et al. (2019) and based on the meteorological conditions as calculated by COSMO-GHG for the location of the power plants. Release-specific parameters were selected from Pregger and Friedrich (2009) considering typical power plant capacities and fuel types.

Two representative release heights were chosen based on the average predicted release height during the observations and the maximum predicted effective release height for the 2 day period (see Figure 3.1 and Table

Figure 3.2: Vertical release profiles for the Belchatów (left) and Jaenschwalde (right) power plant CO₂ tracers given as a Gaussian heights distribution (dashed lines) and mapped onto COSMO levels (symbols).

3.2). From the estimated effective release height and its standard deviation Gaussian release distributions were calculated and mapped onto discrete COSMO model levels as shown in Figure 3.2. For Belchatów both effective release heights resulted in more elevated emissions as in the default GNFR-A profile, whereas for Jaenschwalde one of the resulting profiles (JAEB) was very similar to the GNFR-A profile (JAEA) and the other released the emissions considerably higher (JAEC).

Here, we discuss the results for the tracers BELC and JAEB, for which the most satisfactory comparison results were obtained with the control run. The impact of choosing other release heights (tracers) will be discussed in chapter 3.3 along with the impact of other model settings.

3.2.1.6 Model evaluation against observations

Observations and simulations were compared by a visual analysis of the correspondence between observed and simulated power plant plumes. Next, a straightforward quantitative evaluation strategy was conducted by linearly interpolating in space and time the model output to the location of the observations (both in-situ and total columns). In a second approach the observational data was aggregated within individual grid cells (columns) of the COSMO model. The results were generally similar to those obtained from interpolating model data onto observation location and are not discussed here in detail.

To make the spatial resolution of the observations more comparable to the model resolution, but keeping as much detail as required to describe plume shapes, observations were aggregated from their original temporal resolution to 5 s and 1 s averages for in-situ and remote sensing observations, respectively. The choice of the aggregation interval was roughly based on aircraft speed and distance-to-source, with remote sensing flights being mainly conducted closer to the source and requiring finer detail to resolve the initial plume. The resulting spatial resolution of the observations was generally still finer than that of the model data.

Although all components of atmospheric CO₂ were simulated in COSMO-GHG, for the comparison we mostly focus the discussion on the specific power plant tracers. To extract the power plant signal from the observations a (height-dependent in the case of in-situ data) background concentration was subtracted from the observed signal. The background concentration was either taken from an upstream section of each flight or at a cross-plume location well outside the area of enhanced concentration.

When comparing the total simulated and observed CO₂ dry air mole fractions, obvious biases in the order of 10 ppm were detected (see Figure 3.5). Especially simulated concentrations within the atmospheric boundary layer were larger than in the observations, which may indicate insufficient photosynthetic CO₂ uptake in the

model. When evaluating the vertical CO₂ profiles in the initial and boundary conditions, the same bias was seen. Hence, it seems more likely that the biases were already present in the CAMS model and are not a result of the COSMO-GHG simulation itself. This was especially true for the Bełchatów case with easterly advection and a relatively short distance to the eastern boundary of the COSMO-GHG model (~200 km).

Due to the turbulent and therefore stochastic nature of the investigated plumes, even a perfect model cannot be expected to be able to perfectly represent the observed plume features in space and time. In addition to a direct point-by-point comparison, we therefore also evaluated how well the model captures characteristic features of the observed plume. For this purpose, a Gaussian curve was fitted to the observations/simulations along each flight segment to determine a characteristic width and amplitude for each plume. In addition, the peak location along each transect was aligned between model and observations by calculating the cross correlation function between observations and simulations and shifting the simulations to the estimated maximum of the cross correlation. The aligned data were used to calculate more robust model performance statistics that are less influenced by stochastic discrepancies in the wind and plume direction.

3.2.2 Evaluation of the Bełchatów power plant plume

The exhaust plume of the Bełchatów power stations was targeted by three different aircraft on 7 June 2018 as part of the CoMet campaign. Observations of the plume up to distances of 30 km took place between 12:30 and 15:00 UTC. Local time at Bełchatów is UTC - 1:15. Hence, the first flight transects performed by the FUB Cessna carrying the MAMAP instrument coincided approximately with the foreseen overpass of the CO2M mission. Figure 3.3 shows a snapshot of the simulated power plant plume at 13:45 UTC at 6 different model levels. The general wind direction in the atmospheric boundary layer, which reached up to about 1800 m a.s.l., was from the east to south-east (see Figure 3.5). The atmospheric stratification was unstable in the lowermost part of the boundary layer, neutral in the mid and upper boundary layer and a capping inversion can be seen in both observations and simulations. The simulation shows a very complex plume structure with puff-like elements of enhanced CO₂ at all six vertical levels. In the following, a comparison of the model data against each individual flight is discussed starting with the in-situ observations, which also allowed for a comparison of meteorological parameters.

3.2.2.1 In-situ flight DLR Cessna

The DLR Cessna intersected the power plant plume at three different distances to the source (6.6, 11.8 and 23.6 km) carrying out multi-level curtain flights at the two larger distances (see Figure 3.3 and Table 3.3). Figure 3.3 and Figure 3.4 show some qualitative agreement between the observed and simulated CO₂ enhancements. Especially at shorter distances to the source and lower flight levels (before 14:00 UTC) the location of the plume is rather well matched in the simulation. At larger distances (23.6 km, after 14:20 UTC) the CO₂ enhancements were considerably smaller and less well matched in the simulations. At the highest flight level (2215 m a.s.l., 23.6 km from source) the observation showed no CO₂ enhancement, suggesting that at least up to this distance the plume was confined to the atmospheric boundary layer below this altitude. Again, this observation is well reflected in the simulations (Figure 3.4).

The direct comparison of observed and simulated meteorological parameters (potential temperature, wind speed and direction) showed very good agreement (Figure 3.5). Potential temperatures rose sharply above 1900 m a.s.l. marking the transition from the atmospheric boundary layer to the free troposphere. Potential temperatures below this height were slightly larger in the simulation than in the observations, whereas it was the opposite above the boundary layer top, overall resulting in a somewhat weaker boundary layer inversion in the model. The wind direction within the boundary layer turned from almost easterly at the lowest flight levels to westerly in the free troposphere. Although almost perfectly matching the wind direction within the boundary layer, the transition to the free troposphere was not fully reproduced by the simulation, which showed more south-westerly winds in the free troposphere. Wind speeds in the boundary layer were around 5 m s⁻¹ with strong small scale variability. Average wind speeds were very well matched by the simulation with a small positive bias (0.8 m s⁻¹, 15%), whereas local variability could not be captured. The latter is not surprising as the variability is a manifestation of atmospheric turbulence, which is unpredictable due to its stochastic nature. Furthermore, a large fraction of the observed turbulence is at sub-grid scale in the model and as such cannot be represented in 'mean' wind fields as written out by the model.

Table 3.3: Details of DLR Cessna flight path and QCLS in-situ CO₂ observations on 2018-06-07 intersecting the Bełchatów power plant plume at given cross sections (transect). Maximum CO₂ mole fractions (observations: $C_{o,max}$; model $C_{m,max}$) refer to enhancements above an upstream background value.

Transect	Curtain	Distance (km)	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	Start time (UTC)	$C_{o,max}$ (ppm)	$C_{m,max}$ (ppm)
1	1	6.6	959	13:18	45	32
2	2	11.8	814	13:25	17	17
3	2	11.8	972	13:35	34	12
4	2	11.8	1130	13:43	21	11
5	2	11.8	1282	13:53	17	8
6	2	11.8	1438	13:58	14	11
7	2	11.8	1592	14:05	11	5
8	2	11.8	1745	14:12	6	0.1
9	2	11.8	1903	14:14	11	0.4
10	3	23.6	808	14:31	12	13
11	3	23.6	1123	14:33	13	10
12	3	23.6	954	14:38	14	6
13	3	23.6	1437	14:45	12	5
14	3	23.6	2215	14:52	1	0.5

The direct comparison of observed and simulated CO₂ enhancements (Figure 3.6) showed very good agreement in terms of location and amplitude, especially for the closer and lower flight segments (before 14:00 UTC). The higher flight sections of the second curtain (transects 7 to 9) only showed enhanced CO₂ in the observations but very little in the simulation. At the same time and location, wind directions did not agree as well, indicating that already a small deviation in simulated wind may result in a poor plume representation when comparing directly. At the most distant curtain (23.6 km from the source, transects 10 to 15) the agreement between simulation and observation was not as excellent in terms of plume location but similar plume magnitudes were simulated.

3.2.2.2 In-situ flight DLR Halo

Table 3.4: Details of DLR Halo flight path and CRDS in-situ CO₂ observations on 2018-06-07 intersecting the Bełchatów power plant plume at given cross sections (transect). Maximum CO₂ mole fractions (observations: $C_{o,max}$; model $C_{m,max}$) refer to enhancements above an upstream background value.

Transect	Distance (km)	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	Start time (UTC)	$C_{o,max}$ (ppm)	$C_{m,max}$ (ppm)
5	23.7	1283	13:42	19	14
6	32.8	1283	13:51	17	7

Although mainly focusing on remote-sensing observations and flying at altitudes well above the power plant plume, the DLR Halo aircraft also performed two plume inter-sections at a height of 1280 m a.s.l. and at distances of 23.7 and 32.8 km from the source, respectively (see Table 3.4 and Figure 3.7). Unfortunately, the plume was intercepted at the northern turning points of these transects, where the simulations showed a slightly larger northern extent of the plume than the observations. Otherwise the location of the plume was well matched.

While the DLR Cessna only sampled the atmosphere up to a height of about 2200 m a.s.l., the DLR Halo mostly flew at about 7800 m a.s.l. before descending for the two in-situ plume intersections. Hence, these observations offer a profile comparison over a larger vertical range. They confirm the excellent agreement of potential temperature, wind speed and direction for most of the profile, as seen before for the DLR Cessna observations (Figure 3.9). The observed change in wind direction from westerly/north-westerly in the free troposphere to east/south-easterly in the atmospheric boundary layer was captured by the model, but happened more

Figure 3.3: Snapshot of the simulated CO₂ power plant plume of the Bełchatów power station (black cross) for 2018-06-07 13:45:00 UTC at 6 different model levels (average height given in figure). The black line gives the flight path of the DLR Cessna aircraft carrying out in-situ observations. Observations of CO₂ enhancements (filled circles) at the given time and vertical level are plotted with the same color code as the model simulations.

gradually and over a larger altitude range and a 30 degree bias remained in the lower free troposphere (2000 m a.s.l.). As expected, observed winds showed less variability above the atmospheric boundary layer, but exhibited some larger scale variability that was not fully represented in the model. Again, no large wind biases between model and observations were apparent.

The direct CO₂ comparison (Figure 3.9) indicates only small enhancements in the free troposphere, which, most likely, are not related to recent emissions (as from the power plant) but reflect variability in the free tropospheric background. The two CO₂ peaks observed in the boundary layer and related to the power plant plume, were fairly well matched by the model in terms of location, but were underestimated in peak amplitude.

3.2.2.3 Remote sensing flights FUB Cessna (MAMAP)

The MAMAP spectrometer was operated on two flights over the Bełchatów power plant plume. A total of 14 intersections of the plume were performed at distances from 2 km to 24 km from the source. The aircraft operated at an altitude well above the atmospheric boundary layer top and, hence, can be expected to represent the complete signal from the power plant plume. Qualitatively, vertical column densities of CO₂ as observed by MAMAP and as simulated by COSMO-GHG matched fairly well in terms of location and amplitude for both flights. However, it is apparent that certain features of the simulated plume are very transient and detailed structures of the observations are not captured everywhere and at all times (Figure 3.10). As for the in-situ comparison, one can see large temporal variability in the plume and puff-like structures that are a manifestation of large turbulence elements, which cannot explicitly be matched in any Reynolds averaged simulation of turbulent flows. The simulated puff-like structures dissolve at larger distances from the source (>20 km) suggesting that dispersion of the plume across the scales of the large turbulent elements was complete and that at these distances any plume observation will less critically depend on the exact time of observation.

When comparing simulated time series of total column CO₂ to observations (Figure 3.11), the much smoother character of the simulations can be explained by the model resolution and the fact that at short distances from the source the simulated plume only extended over a few grid cells. Furthermore, observational noise was considerably larger than for in-situ observations. Peak locations and shapes were frequently well reproduced

Figure 3.4: Vertical cross section of simulated CO₂ power plant plume of the Bełchatów power station for 2018-06-07 along the flight track of the DLR Cessna. Observations of CO₂ enhancements (filled circles) are plotted with the same color code as the model simulations.

(for example differently steep plume shoulders in flight segments 2 and 3 of second flight), whereas at other times the simulation was lacking finer structures (for example the double peak in flight segment 2 of the first flight). The direct comparison also reveals more favourable comparison statistics for the second flight with a considerably larger correlation coefficient.

3.2.2.4 Remote sensing flight DLR Halo (CHARM-F)

The CHARM-F lidar on board of the DLR Halo aircraft was used to collect four transects of the Bełchatów power plant plume at distances between 2 km and 6 km from the source. The flight took place between the two MAMAP flights under the same kind of turbulent plume conditions as described above. The large noise level of the CHARM-F observations makes a visual comparison relatively difficult (Figure 3.12). However, the largest observed vertical column densities generally agreed with the location of the simulated plume. The direct comparison of the observed and simulated time series along the flight revealed the large noise level in the observations, which had a similar magnitude as the simulated plume amplitude (Figure 3.13). Nevertheless, reasonable agreement of the plume locations can be seen, but peak column densities were much smaller in the simulations, which may partly be related to model resolution. Maximal total columns observed by CHARM-F at the different transects were considerably larger (range 18 - 62 x 10¹⁹ molec.cm⁻²) than those observed by MAMAP (range 9 - 42 x 10¹⁹ molec.cm⁻²). Differences may be due to tempo-spatial variability of the plume and different integration intervals and noise levels of the instruments. Simulated maximum total columns along the same flight tracks were more similar for the different flights and generally lower than observed maxima (range 2 - 17 x 10¹⁹ molec.cm⁻²).

3.2.3 Evaluation of the Jaenschwalde power plant plume

The Jaenschwalde power plant plume was intercepted by two different aircraft (FUB Cessna and DLR Halo) on 2018-05-23. Both aircraft sampled the plume in the morning hours between 8:30 and 11:00 UTC. Considering the local time at Jaenschwalde (UTC - 1:00) all flights took place before the foreseen overpass time of the CO₂M mission. The simulated wind direction (no meteorological observations were carried out by the low-flying FUB

Figure 3.5: Vertical profiles (top) and scatter plots (bottom) of observed (blue) and simulated (red) meteorological parameters along the flight track of the DLR Cessna: potential temperature (a), wind speed (b), wind direction (c), and total CO₂ mole fractions (d).

Cessna) at plume height was from the east turning to the north-east during the period of observation. At the same time, simulated wind speeds were decreasing from a maximum of 10 m s^{-1} to around 7 m s^{-1} . The stability in the atmospheric boundary layer was slightly stable, becoming more neutral to slightly unstable over time. No clear capping inversion was visible in the simulated temperature profiles.

3.2.3.1 In-situ flight FUB Cessna

A single in-situ curtain flight was carried out at a distance of about 9 km downwind of Jaenschwalde. Different to the Bełchatów plume, the simulated Jaenschwalde plume showed much less spatial variability and no puff-like structures, but rather a Gaussian shape. Only at higher altitudes individual puff structures are visible in the snapshot presented in Figure 3.14. Previous to the curtain flight, the FUB Cessna was flying at an altitude of about 1500 m a.s.l., which according to the simulations was well above the top of the mixed layer and the power plant plume (Figure 3.15). However, some enhanced CO₂ concentrations were observed at this altitude as well (see Figures 3.15 and 3.16). These were not at all reproduced by the simulation. However, it is interesting to note that in this case the simulated power plant plume was not as isolated as in the case of Bełchatów. Other CO₂ sources contributed to considerably enhanced concentrations outside the Jaenschwalde plume (not shown). When the aircraft finally commenced the curtain flight below 1500 m a.s.l. it observed very pronounced CO₂ enhancements at 1400 and 1250 m a.s.l. that were clearly associated with the Jaenschwalde plume. These enhancements were mostly underestimated by the model. The highest observed peak concentrations occurred

Figure 3.6: Time series (left) and scatter plot (right) of observed (blue) and simulated (red) power plant CO₂ along the flight track of the DLR Cessna. Gray shaded areas and numbering refer to different plume inter-sections.

at an altitude range from 1000 to 1250 m a.s.l., whereas simulated peak concentrations were largest at lower levels (500 m a.s.l.). Hence, it seems like the plume in COSMO-GHG had a much smaller vertical extent than the observed plume, either resulting from an underestimation of vertical mixing or an underestimation of the effective release height. However, the model performance did not significantly improve when simulating the plume with a higher release height. The curtain plot (Figure 3.15) reveals that the vertical extent of the simulated plume increased over the course of the flight, which seems to indicate that the timing of the boundary layer growth in the morning was not well captured by the model and was happening too late. This could be a general challenge for atmospheric models that usually perform worse in transient situations than in situations with relatively constant surface forcings.

Besides these apparent discrepancies in vertical extent, the location and width of the simulated plume at lower altitudes matched the in-situ observation rather well, while the amplitudes were considerably underestimated at all but the lowest level (flight segments 3 to 6 in Figure 3.16). This under-prediction by the model plus the smaller vertical extent of the plume may indicate that wind speeds were too large in the model, leading to an excessive initial dilution of the emitted plume or that actual emissions at the time of observation were considerably larger than assumed in the simulation. Furthermore, it is apparent from Figure 3.15 that large fractions of the simulated plume remained at levels below the lowest observed level. It is possible that the real plume was more detached from the surface and, hence, carried a similar load as the simulated plume, just at higher altitudes. Without additional observations closer to the ground, this discussion remains speculative.

3.2.3.2 Remote sensing flight FUB Cessna (MAMAP)

The MAMAP instrument on board the FUB Cessna intercepted the plume at 7 distances from the source. As can be seen from the qualitative comparison (Figure 3.17), plume locations do not perfectly align between observations and simulations. The plume was observed slightly further north as compared to the simulations, which is in contrast to the in-situ comparison, but may well be explained by the spatio-temporal variability of the plume direction and the fact that the MAMAP observations took place earlier than the in-situ observations. The quantitative comparison of the CO₂ vertical column densities along the flight track shows this mismatch in plume location, which was especially pronounced for flight segments 5 and 6. The observed peak heights and spatial variability were underestimated by the model, which simulated a much smoother shape. Most of these discrepancies may be due to the limited spatial resolution of the model. A more detailed discussion of plume amplitudes and widths is presented in Section 3.2.4. The mismatch in plume location increased when releasing it at a higher altitude above ground, further indicating that the vertical mismatch of the plume, as seen from the in-situ observations, may be more related to a delay of boundary layer growth and vertical mixing than to the initial plume height.

Figure 3.7: Snapshot of the simulated CO₂ power plant plume of the Belchatów power station (black cross) for 2018-06-07 13:30:00 UTC at 6 different model levels (average height given in figure). The black line gives the flight path of the DLR Halo aircraft carrying out remote sensing and in-situ observations. In-situ observations of CO₂ enhancements (filled circles) at the given time and vertical level are plotted with the same color code as the model simulations.

3.2.3.3 Remote sensing flight DLR Halo (CHARM-F)

Further observations of the Jaenschwalde power plant plume were collected by the CHARM-F instrument on board of the DLR Halo (same as for Beromünster). The aircraft flew a total of 10 transects of which two were upwind of the source and the remainder downwind at distances from 0.2 km to 14 km. Flights took place at a similar time as those by the MAMAP instrument. CHARM-F data were characterised by a large level of noise, which makes a comparison more challenging (Figure 3.19) even when applying a longer averaging window (4 s) to the observations. When comparing the interpolated model data against the observations (Figure 3.20), the instrumental noise largely dominates the time-series. In addition, there were several negative excursions of the observed total columns from the baseline, which seem to indicate less robust measurement conditions than for the CHARM-F flights at Belchatów. However, it is remarkable that some of the major observed peaks were well reproduced by the model in terms of amplitude and location, which is also reflected in the scatter plot and a reasonable correlation coefficient. The observations do not exhibit clear Gaussian plume features on most transects. When fitting a Gaussian curve to the individual transects, robust results were only obtained for transects 4, 5, and 10. For the other transects either the explained variance of the Gaussian fit or the estimated error probability were not satisfactory (see Section 3.2.4).

3.2.4 Summary of plume comparison

To summarise the performance of COSMO-GHG in simulating power plant plumes in the near field (distance shorter 30 km), Figure (3.21) presents performance statistics for all individual flights in the form of a target plot and a Taylor diagram, respectively. These statistics were obtained from the location-optimised time-series that shifted the simulated plume to optimally match the observed plume along individual transects. Hence, statistics for individual flights may appear more favourable than in the individual (non-shifted) time-series presented above. Common features from all individual flights are modest negative model biases, an underestimation of observed variability by the model, and normalised RMSE between 0.5 and 1 with respect to observed variability. The first two points indicate that observed power plant CO₂ mole fractions and vertical column

Figure 3.8: Vertical profiles (top) and scatter plots (bottom) of observed (blue) and simulated (red) meteorological parameters along the flight track of the DLR Halo: potential temperature (a), wind speed (b), wind direction (c), and total CO₂ mole fractions (d).

densities were generally underestimated by the model. The amount of variance explained by the model ranged from about 80 % for the in-situ measurements in Bełchatów down to only 25 % for the CHARM-F measurements in Jaenschwalde. Large parts of the unexplained variance is likely attributable to instrument noise (especially in case of CHARM-F) and high-resolution features not resolvable at the given model resolution. Both effects were most pronounced for the CHARM-F instrument but apparent as well for MAMAP observations close to the source.

It is interesting to note that despite the more complex plume structure observed in Bełchatów, model performance was generally better for this case. The flight in Jaenschwalde took place earlier in the day than in Bełchatów. At this time the atmospheric boundary layer is generally developing fast with time due to the quickly changing surface forcings. Hence, the model may be more challenged to correctly match the more transient nature of the situation. In contrast, the flight in Bełchatów took place in a very convective, but fully developed, boundary layer. On the one hand, the latter may be more challenging when it comes to simulating individual large eddies that determine plume dispersion in the near-field of the release, on the other hand, surface forcings, mean wind direction and boundary layer height change less over time at this point of the diurnal cycle, making it easier for the model to follow the temporal developments.

Figure 3.22 analyses the estimated plume widths and amplitudes from all plume transects as a function of distance from the source for the Bełchatów case. It should be kept in mind that for very narrow plumes close to the source this analysis may be limited by the spatial resolution of the model. In addition, the observed and

Figure 3.9: Time series (left) and scatter plot (right) of observed (blue) and simulated (red) CO₂ from the power plant Bełchatów along the flight track of the DLR Halo. Gray shaded areas and numbering refer to different plume inter-sections.

simulated plumes showed more detailed structures than a Gaussian curve can accommodate.

Plume widths for distances shorter than 8 km from the source were rather well matched by the model for both remote sensing and in-situ observations. With increasing distance there was more disagreement with the model generally predicting wider plumes than observed. From the observations only a weak general widening of the plume was determined, whereas for the simulated plume the widening with distance was very apparent and depending on altitude as well. At some altitudes observed and simulated plume width agreed well, whereas for other altitudes plume widths were largely overestimated by the model. Plume widths agreed well between different observing platforms and methods, which is remarkable considering the complex plume structure and large temporal-spatial variability.

Plume amplitudes were more often under- than overestimated by the model at all distances from the source. Especially close to the source and for the remote sensing observations large differences were apparent. Part of this underestimation can be explained by the larger plume width. When looking at the integral of the Gaussian curve fits along a transect (not shown), the differences between observations and simulations were relatively small for in-situ flights and at distances larger 8 km, whereas they were large for shorter distances, mostly represented by remote-sensing observations. Once more, the larger differences at short distances may be related to the large simulated variability of the plume at short distances (also see section 3.2.5) and result from tempo-spatial mismatches of the plume location.

Similar results were obtained for Jaenschwalde, where plume widths and amplitudes also tended to be overestimated and underestimated by the model, respectively. In strong contrast to the Bełchatów case, plume widths remained smaller than 3 km up to distances of 18 km from the source. The in-situ data of the plume, which was all collected at the same distance (9.3 km), showed large scatter for both observed and simulated plumes. The plume got continuously wider with distance from source, as determined from the total columns, with relative differences between observations and simulations becoming smaller. A considerable fraction of the overestimation of plume width may have resulted from the limited model resolution of 1 km, setting a lower limit of simulated plume width. Once again, there was a fairly good agreement between plume widths determined from the different remote sensing platforms, although the noisy character of the CHARM-F observations only allowed for reliable Gaussian fits at three distances. Plume amplitudes were generally larger in the observations than the simulations and decreased steadily with distance from the source. Resulting integrals along the plume transect (not shown) remained smaller in the simulation than in the observations up to distances of 10 km. This may indicate an overestimated wind speed or underestimated source strength in the simulations as already discussed above.

Table 3.5: Details of FUB Cessna flight path and MAMAP CO₂ vertical column density observations on 2018-06-07 intersecting the Bełchatów power plant plume at given cross sections (transect). Maximum CO₂ vertical columns (observations: $C_{o,max}$; model $C_{m,max}$) refer to enhancements above an upstream background value.

Flight	Transect	Distance (km)	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	Start time (UTC)	$C_{o,max}$ (molec.cm ⁻²)	$C_{m,max}$ (molec.cm ⁻²)
1	1	2.0	2850	12:29	42 x 10 ¹⁹	17 x 10 ¹⁹
1	2	3.0	2850	12:40	12 x 10 ¹⁹	9.1 x 10 ¹⁹
1	3	4.0	2850	12:47	21 x 10 ¹⁹	7.5 x 10 ¹⁹
1	4	5.9	2850	12:57	9.2 x 10 ¹⁹	2.2 x 10 ¹⁹
1	5	9.6	2850	13:32	8.5 x 10 ¹⁹	3.5 x 10 ¹⁹
1	6	12.4	2850	13:07	11 x 10 ¹⁹	3.0 x 10 ¹⁹
1	7	23.8	2850	13:23	6.8 x 10 ¹⁹	3.2 x 10 ¹⁹
2	1	2.0	2850	13:50	34 x 10 ¹⁹	11 x 10 ¹⁹
2	2	3.0	2850	14:00	30 x 10 ¹⁹	10 x 10 ¹⁹
2	3	4.0	2850	14:06	22 x 10 ¹⁹	7.3 x 10 ¹⁹
2	4	5.9	2850	14:16	15 x 10 ¹⁹	3.9 x 10 ¹⁹
2	5	9.7	2850	14:22	6.8 x 10 ¹⁹	3.3 x 10 ¹⁹
2	6	12.5	2850	14:33	7.9 x 10 ¹⁹	2.5 x 10 ¹⁹
2	7	23.9	2850	14:42	8.3 x 10 ¹⁹	2.2 x 10 ¹⁹

Table 3.6: Details of DLR Halo flight path and CHARM-F CO₂ vertical column density observations on 2018-06-07 intersecting the Bełchatów power plant plume at given cross sections (transect). Maximum CO₂ vertical column densities (observations: $C_{o,max}$; model $C_{m,max}$) refer to enhancements above an upstream background value.

Transect	Distance (km)	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	Start time (UTC)	$C_{o,max}$ (molec.cm ⁻²)	$C_{m,max}$ (molec.cm ⁻²)
1	2.1	7890	13:09	62 x 10 ¹⁹	12 x 10 ¹⁹
2	3.3	7890	13:16	38 x 10 ¹⁹	8.0 x 10 ¹⁹
3	4.2	7890	13:23	33 x 10 ¹⁹	7.9 x 10 ¹⁹
4	6.0	7870	13:30	18 x 10 ¹⁹	6.8 x 10 ¹⁹

3.2.5 Analysis of simulated spatio-temporal variability of power plant plume

One major challenge in comparing observed and simulated plumes was the large spatio-temporal variability of the plume encountered in the very turbulent atmospheric boundary layer. Such variability may also affect any emission estimation based on individual snapshots as taken from polar orbiting satellite observations. In an attempt to quantify the potential impact of plume variability, the simulated variability was evaluated at the original resolution of the model and at a resolution similar to that expected from the CO2M mission (2 km x 2 km). The temporal standard deviation of simulated vertical CO₂ column densities (power plant tracer only) was calculated for the period of observation of the Bełchatów case (12:00 to 15:00 UTC, including 13 model snapshots) and divided by the mean vertical column densities during this period. This relative standard deviation clearly showed that large areas of the initial plume up to distances of about 15 km from the source were extremely variable with relative standard deviations larger than 100% for many grid cells (Figure 3.24). Smaller values of variability were only simulated for a narrow core of the initial plume and at larger distances. Observing the plume at lower resolution somewhat reduced the area of increased variability.

Figure 3.25 summarizes these findings, showing a box-plot of relative standard deviations as function of distance from the source. The relative standard deviation was largest at distances below 15 km, with slightly larger values for the lower resolution output. Beyond 15 km distance relative standard deviations decreased continuously and differences between higher and lower resolution were small. However, at high resolution more grid cells with very large values were identified (outliers marked by dots in Figure 3.25).

In contrast to the simulated plume of the Bełchatów power plant, the Jaenschwalde plume showed much less

Figure 3.10: Snapshot of the simulated total column CO₂ power plant plume of the Belchatów power station (black cross) for 2018-06-07 12:15 UTC (top left), 12:45 UTC (top right), 14:00 UTC (bottom left), 14:30 UTC (bottom right). The black line gives the flight path of the FUB Cessna aircraft carrying out remote sensing observations with the MAMAP instrument. Observations of CO₂ enhancements (filled circles) at the given time are plotted with the same color code as the model simulations.

spatio-temporal variability. This is further supported by the analysis of variability of the model output that showed much smaller relative variability in the initial Jaenschwalde plume (less than 10 km from the source) than for the the Belchatów plume. Even at high resolution, only the fringes of the plume were very variable. At lower resolution the number of grid cells with large variability was even smaller.

When analysing the relative variability by distance from the source (Figure 3.26), it is apparent that median values of relative variability remained below or close to 50% at all distances, whereas in the convective plume of the Belchatów case such levels were only estimated at distances beyond 25 km from the source. It is also interesting to note that in the Jaenschwalde case the decrease of variability with distance was not as pronounced as for the Belchatów case. On the contrary, variability did not decrease beyond 20 km from the source, including some extreme outliers present at all distances for high resolution data. One potential reason for this behaviour could be that small changes in wind direction over time contributed to large variability at the fringes of the plume.

The meteorological conditions encountered during the observation of the Jaenschwalde plume (slightly stable to neutral), hence, seem to be more favourable for observing a representative plume in a single snapshot/overflight than the unstable/convective conditions during the Belchatów observations, which resulted in a very variable plume structure. The observations in Jaenschwalde were taken earlier in the day than those in Belchatów,

Figure 3.11: Time series (left) and scatter plot (right) of observed (blue) and simulated (red) total column CO_2 from the power plant Belchatów along the two flights of the FUB Cessna.

analysed here 07:00 to 10:00 LT versus 10:45 to 13:45 LT, respectively. Considering that the encountered situations are typical for summer fair-weather periods, our findings suggest that CO_2M observations taken at an overpass time of 11:00 LT may often be taken under convective conditions. Near field interpretations of plumes emerging from large point sources should take the potentially large temporal variability of such plumes into account, e.g. by applying larger uncertainties to transport simulations of the near field. Nevertheless, the envisaged overpass time seems in general more suitable from the model perspective because it coincides with a time of day with small changes of the surface forcings and, hence, a generally less transient state of the atmospheric boundary layer, which should be easier to capture by atmospheric transport models.

The limited temporal resolution with which model output was stored (every 15 minutes) may well have led to an underestimation of variability in this assessment and the results should be seen as a lower limit of the true observable variability.

In order to illustrate that the simulated differences in terms of plume variability agrees with the observed plume variability, all observations (in-situ and remote sensing) for each case were combined in a single plot (Figure 3.28). It is apparent that the horizontal spread of observations with enhanced CO_2 levels perpendicular to the plume direction was multiple times larger for Belchatow than for Jaenschwalde, whereas observed plume widths on individual transects differed only by around a factor of two between the two cases (compare Figures 3.22) and 3.23). The additional increase in the variability indicates that temporal variability of the observed plume location, and not just plume dispersion, was larger for Belchatow than for Jaenschwalde, hence, supporting the results obtained from COSMO-GHG.

Figure 3.12: Snapshot of the simulated total column CO₂ power plant plume of the Belchatów power station (black cross) for 2018-06-07 13:00 UTC (left) and 13:15 UTC (right). The black line gives the flight path of the DLR Halo aircraft carrying out remote sensing observations with the CHARM-F instrument. Observations of CO₂ enhancements (filled circles) at the given time are plotted with the same color code as the model simulations.

3.2.6 Berlin city plume: 2015-08-11 and 2015-09-29

Only a brief qualitative comparison between the AirMAP NO₂ observations for the city of Berlin and COSMO-GHG simulations is given here. Note that COSMO-GHG did not simulate NO₂ in a full chemistry run, but rather with a simplified first-order decay mechanism only. Hence, next to differences in the transport simulation, effects of faster or slower decay during the specific conditions encountered on the days of observation or non-linear interactions with other nitrogen species and ozone may contribute to model-observation mismatches.

Qualitatively, there is a good agreement between observed and simulated plume locations on both days, which were considerably different in the observed NO₂ levels, plume structure and direction. On both days, Berlin did not appear as a broad uniform source of NO₂, but rather individual strong point sources dominate the picture. Unfortunately, a large part of the city was not covered by the observations on 11 Aug 2015, so that the comparison has to focus on the western part of the city. Observed and simulated vertical column densities were comparable, although observed column densities were slightly larger than in the simulations, especially on the second flight on 28 Sep 2015. Part of this mismatch may result from the different timing of observations

Figure 3.13: Time series (left) and scatter plot (right) of observed by CHARM-F (blue) and simulated (red) total column CO₂ from the power plant Belchatów along the flight track of the DLR Halo.

Table 3.7: Details of FUB Cessna flight path and QCLS in-situ CO₂ observations on 2018-05-23 intersecting the Jaenschwalde power plant plume at given cross sections (transect). Maximum CO₂ mole fractions (observations: $C_{o,max}$; model $C_{m,max}$) refer to enhancements above an upstream background value.

Transect	Curtain	Distance (km)	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	Start time (UTC)	$C_{o,max}$ (ppm)	$C_{m,max}$ (ppm)
1	1	9.3	1409	10:06	25	0.2
2	1	9.3	1254	10:15	30	4.5
3	1	9.3	1097	10:23	30	9.2
4	1	9.3	936	10:32	19	9.7
5	1	9.5	780	10:39	15	6.2
6	1	8.8	488	10:45	15	19

Table 3.8: Details of FUB Cessna flight path and MAMAP CO₂ vertical column density observations on 2018-05-23 intersecting the Jaenschwalde power plant plume at given cross sections (transect). Maximum CO₂ vertical columns (observations: $C_{o,max}$; model $C_{m,max}$) refer to enhancements above an upstream background value.

Transect	Distance (km)	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	Start time (UTC)	$C_{o,max}$ (molec.cm ⁻²)	$C_{m,max}$ (molec.cm ⁻²)
1	0.8	1522	09:00	25×10^{19}	7.9×10^{19}
2	4.9	1525	09:10	13×10^{19}	5.6×10^{19}
3	6.2	1533	09:16	10×10^{19}	5.2×10^{19}
4	9.3	1528	09:23	10×10^{19}	4.8×10^{19}
5	13.1	1527	09:33	7.2×10^{19}	4.7×10^{19}
6	15.3	1529	09:37	9.2×10^{19}	3.8×10^{19}
7	18.4	1534	09:44	9.1×10^{19}	3.7×10^{19}

versus simulations. A remarkable difference between model and observations on 28 Sep 2015 is the fact that NO₂ total columns tend to decrease with distance in the simulations but to increase in the observations. One reason could be an incorrect partitioning of NO_x between NO and NO₂ in the model. NO_x is primarily emitted in the form of NO and is then gradually converted to NO₂ by reaction with O₃. If O₃ levels are low compared to the levels of NO_x, then this conversion can be strongly suppressed and NO_x would remain in the form of NO over long distances along the plume. In the model, however, which uses a very simple parameterisation of the partitioning, NO_x is likely converted to NO₂ too rapidly.

Another reason for the difference could be biases in the air mass factors used to convert observed slant column densities into vertical column densities (VCDs). With increasing distance from Berlin, the plume may rise in altitude. If NO₂ is placed too low in the a priori profiles used in the retrieval, then NO₂ VCD could be significantly overestimated. In order to compare observations and model simulations in a more quantitative way, the averaging kernels would have to be accounted for.

The comparison underlines that COSMO-GHG, when driven with an accurate high-resolution emission inventory, is able to capture fine-scale features in the plumes of Berlin also seen in the observations, but it also suggests that a better representation of the NO_x chemistry is required and that for a more quantitative comparison the model profiles need to be multiplied with the averaging kernels of the NO₂ retrievals.

Figure 3.14: Snapshot of the simulated CO₂ power plant plume of the Jaenschwalde power station (black cross) for 2018-05-23 10:30:00 UTC at 6 different model levels (average height given in figure). The black line gives the flight path of the FUB Cessna aircraft carrying out remote sensing and in-situ observations. Observations of CO₂ enhancements (filled circles) at the given time and vertical level are plotted with the same color code as the model simulations.

Figure 3.15: Vertical cross section of simulated CO₂ power plant plume of the Jaenschwalde power station for 2018-05-23 along the flight track of the FUB Cessna. Observations of CO₂ enhancements (filled circles) are plotted with the same color code as the model simulations.

Figure 3.16: Time series (left) and scatter plot (right) of observed (blue) and simulated (red) CO₂ from the power plant Jaenschwalde along the flight track of the FUB Cessna.

Figure 3.17: Snapshot of the simulated total column CO₂ power plant plume of the Jaenschwalde power station (black cross) for 2018-05-23 09:00 UTC (left) and 09:30 UTC (right). The black line gives the flight path of the FUB Cessna aircraft carrying out remote sensing observations with the MAMAP instrument. Observations of CO₂ enhancements (filled circles) at the given time are plotted with the same color code as the model simulations.

Table 3.9: Details of DLR Halo flight path and CHARM-F CO₂ vertical column density observations on 2018-05-23 intersecting the Jaenschwalde power plant plume at given cross sections (transect). Maximum CO₂ vertical columns (observations: $C_{o,max}$; model $C_{m,max}$) refer to enhancements above an upstream background value. Transects 2 and 6 were flown upstream of the source.

Transect	Distance (km)	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	Start time (UTC)	$C_{o,max}$ (molec.cm ⁻²)	$C_{m,max}$ (molec.cm ⁻²)
1	9.6	7890	08:28	13 x 10 ¹⁹	2.6 x 10 ¹⁹
3	4.7	7890	08:40	8.8 x 10 ¹⁹	4.2 x 10 ¹⁹
4	1.5	7870	08:48	1.6 x 10 ¹⁹	7.4 x 10 ¹⁹
5	4.7	7870	08:56	9.5 x 10 ¹⁹	5.5 x 10 ¹⁹
7	1.4	7870	09:09	24 x 10 ¹⁹	7.7 x 10 ¹⁹
8	0.1	7870	09:17	7.0 x 10 ¹⁹	8.4 x 10 ¹⁹
9	1.4	7870	09:25	14 x 10 ¹⁹	7.1 x 10 ¹⁹
10	13.8	7870	09:30	7.1 x 10 ¹⁹	4.7 x 10 ¹⁹

Figure 3.18: Time series (left) and scatter plot (right) of observed (blue) and simulated (red) total column CO₂ from the power plant Jaenschwalde along the flight track of the FUB Cessna.

Figure 3.19: Snapshot of the simulated total column CO₂ power plant plume of the Jaenschwalde power station (black cross) for 2018-05-23 08:30 UTC (left) and 09:00 UTC (right). The black line gives the flight path of the DLR Halo aircraft carrying out remote sensing observations with the CHARM-F instrument. Observations of CO₂ enhancements (filled circles) at the given time are plotted with the same color code as the model simulations.

Figure 3.20: Time series (left) and scatter plot (right) of observed (blue) and simulated (red) total column CO₂ from the power plant Jaenschwalde along the flight track of the DLR Halo.

Figure 3.21: Target (left) and Taylor (right) plot summarising performance statistics for all flight observations, adjusted for shift along each flight transect. Different flights/instruments are displayed by different colors, while different symbols indicate the two power plants. In the target plot two parameters, bias-adjusted RMSE (BRMSE; x-axis) and bias (y-axis), are normalised by the standard deviation of the reference (observations). A perfect model would fall onto the origin. The distance between the origin and any given point is the normalised RMSE. Points are drawn with a negative (positive) BRMS if model standard deviation is smaller (larger) than the standard deviation of the reference. For points within the circle with radius one, the variance of the residuals is smaller than the variance of the reference. In the Taylor plot two further aspects of the comparison are displayed: the correlation coefficient as angular distance from the vertical and the standard deviation of the model normalised by the standard deviation on the radial axis. Furthermore, the Taylor skill score (combining these two aspects of the comparison and using $R_0=0.9$) is given as dashed-dotted isolines.

Figure 3.22: Summary of observed and simulated plume characteristics for all observations/simulations of the Bełchatów power plant plume. Plume width (top) and plume amplitude (bottom) as calculated from fitting a Gaussian curve to the observations/simulations along each flight segment intersecting the plume.

Figure 3.23: Summary of observed and simulated plume characteristics for all observations/simulations of the Jaenschwalde power plant plume. Plume width (left) and plume amplitude (right) as calculated from fitting a Gaussian curve to the observations/simulations along each flight segment intersecting the plume.

Figure 3.24: Mean (left) and relative standard deviation (right) of the simulated total column CO₂ resulting from the Bełchatów power plant plume for the period of observations (12:00 to 15:00 UTC) and for two horizontal resolutions: original model (top) and 2 km x 2 km (bottom). The relative standard deviation was cropped to areas with column densities greater 1×10^{19} molecules cm⁻¹

Figure 3.25: Box-plot of relative standard deviation of the simulated total column CO₂ resulting from the Bełchatów power plant plume for the period of observations (2018-06-07 12:00 to 15:00 UTC) and for two horizontal resolutions: original model (1 km x 1 km) and 2 km x 2 km (bottom).

Figure 3.26: Box-plot of relative standard deviation of the simulated total column CO₂ resulting from the Jaenschwalde power plant plume for the period of observations (2018-05-23 08:00 to 11:00 UTC) and for two horizontal resolutions: original model (1 km x 1 km) and 2 km x 2 km (bottom).

Figure 3.27: Mean (left) and relative standard deviation (right) of the simulated Jaenschwalde power plant plume for the period of observations (08:00 to 11:00 UTC) for two horizontal resolutions: original model (top) and 2 km x 2 km (bottom). The relative standard deviation was cropped to areas with column densities greater 5×10^{18} molecules cm^{-2}

Figure 3.28: Perspective overlay of all available flight observations of CO₂ for the Belchatow, 2018-06-07, (left) and Jaenschwalde, 2018-05-23, (right) power plant plume. Only observations with mole fraction enhancements large 5 ppm and vertical column enhancements larger 2×10^{19} are given as colored symbols. For all other observations only the location of these observations is indicated by black dots. In-situ data are plotted at the actual altitude of the observation, whereas remote sensing data are plotted at half the atmospheric boundary layer height. Only observations up to a distance of about 15 km from the source are shown.

Figure 3.29: Comparison of the NO₂ plume of Berlin as observed with AirMAP spectrometer (left) and simulated with COSMO-GHG (right) for two days in August/September 2015. Note that the acquisition of the AirMAP data stretched over several hours, whereas snapshots at the end of the acquisition period are shown for COSMO-GHG.

3.3 Impact of COSMO-GHG model settings on plume simulations

In the present chapter we examine the influence of different settings of COSMO-GHG on the transport simulations for the two power plant plumes discussed in Chapter 3.2. The analysis mainly focuses on model performance statistics and how they are influenced by model settings. Model settings that were varied included the use of observation nudging (not employed during SMARTCARB phase 1), different settings of the turbulence scheme, and emission release heights. The impact of these settings on meteorology and CO₂ as well as an analysis of the overall ensemble variability is presented.

3.3.1 Methods

Table 3.10: Overview of COSMO-GHG sensitivity simulations and their specific model settings.

Case	Nudging	Turbulence	TKE horiz.	TKE non-local	TKE therm.
CTRL	on	COSMO	NA	NA	NA
NONUDGE	off	COSMO	NA	NA	NA
TURB1	on	ICON	on	off	off
TURB3	on	ICON	off	on	off
TURB4	on	ICON	off	off	on
TURB134	on	ICON	on	on	on

The 'CTRL' run used the model settings as described in detail in section 3.2.1.4. For an additional model sensitivity run, 'NONUDGE', the meteorological observation nudging was switched off. This configuration comes closest to the one used during SMARTCARB phase 1. However, a more advanced version of COSMO-GHG was used here and it could not be tested how different the two versions are. COSMO-GHG prior to version 5.04 employed a prognostic turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) equation and a level 2.5 closure (Mellor and Yamada, 1982). The closure assumes local equilibrium for all moments except for TKE, for which advection and turbulent transport are considered. Previous COSMO-GHG simulations employed during SMARTCARB phase 1 were based on this turbulence scheme, as were the CTRL and NONUDGE runs. In addition to this old 'COSMO' turbulence scheme, the newer versions of COSMO-GHG also include a new turbulence scheme which was developed for the use in the next-generation climate and weather model ICON. This new scheme allows for a more precise description of the TKE budget including fine-tuning of the TKE contributions from different processes. Four different configurations of the new turbulence scheme were tested here, all of which employed meteorological observation nudging as well. The first of these sensitivity runs 'TURB1' considered additional TKE production by horizontal shear (default is to consider only vertical shear of the horizontal wind). The second sensitivity run 'TURB3' considered non-local calculations of vertical gradients in the TKE budget, whereas the 'TURB4' sensitivity run considered TKE as a source in the enthalpy budget. The final sensitivity run 'TURB134' combined all three of these switches.

Next to the general model settings, which mainly influence the meteorological conditions simulated by the model, the vertical release profiles for the power plant emissions were varied and simulated by three different tracers (for details see 3.2.1.5). Tracers are labeled BELA, BELB, BELC and JAEA, JAEB, JAEC for the Belchatów and Jaenschwalde power station, respectively. Note that BELC and JAEB were used for the discussion in the previous section and hence 'CTRL BELC' and 'CTRL JAEB' present our control tracers. The three different tracers were used in each of the six model sensitivity runs, and hence a total of 18 different tracer simulations was evaluated.

3.3.2 Results

3.3.2.1 Changes in meteorology and plume structure

The different model settings were expected to have a direct impact on the meteorological fields predicted by COSMO-GHG. The chosen settings mostly focused on the description of turbulence and, hence, impacts

Figure 3.30: Vertical profiles of simulated areal mean wind direction (left), wind speed (middle), and potential temperature (right) for a domain approximately 50 km x 50 km around the Bełchatów power plant on 2018-06-07. Ribbons give temporal evolution over period of observations (13:15 to 15:00 UTC). Colors indicate different model configurations. Observations taken from DLR Cessna shown as black symbols.

on the meteorological variables were expected to be largest in the atmospheric boundary layer. Figure 3.30 shows vertical model profiles of wind direction, wind speed, and potential temperature for the Bełchatów case, comparing directly with in-situ observations as obtained by the DLR Cessna aircraft. Differences in wind speed and direction were relatively small. The NONUDGE case showed slightly increased wind speeds in the boundary layer, whereas the TURB1 and TURB134 cases experienced slightly lower wind speeds. At the top of the boundary layer wind direction changes happened at higher altitudes for the NONUDGE case, which was less in line with observations. A stronger impact of meteorological data nudging was visible for the temperature profile. Nudging led to a considerably better agreement of the temperature within the boundary layer and to an improved, though not perfect, representation of the capping temperature inversion. Differences between the different turbulence settings, which all employed meteorological nudging, were generally small.

For the Jaenschwalde case no meteorological observations were available in the atmospheric boundary layer. Hence, differences in the simulated meteorological profiles between the sensitivity runs can only be compared against each other. As for the Bełchatów case the run most different from all others was the one without nudging (NONUDGE) (Figure 3.31). Wind speeds in this case showed a peak at 800 a.s.l., which was less pronounced in the the other simulations. Wind directions were considerably different above 1000 a.s.l. In the NONUDGE case, the temperature profile featured a shallow neutral layer early in the morning, which was topped by a more stable area above and which deepened during the course of the morning. All other sensitivity runs indicated a less stable stratification up to 2000 m a.s.l. The profiles also illustrate the larger changes in meteorological conditions over time as compared with the Bełchatów case.

3.3.2.2 Influence on plume simulations vs. observations

Despite the modest influence of the model settings on the shape of the mean vertical profiles of meteorological variables (except for the NONUDGE case), very different power plant CO₂ plumes resulted in the simulations as illustrated in Figure 3.32 showing a snapshot of total column XCO₂ of the Bełchatów plume from all 6 model realisations for the BELC tracer (highest release). Plume structures were especially different in the near-field (<20 km from the source) where different turbulent elements are easily distinguishable. The general advection direction of the plume agreed fairly well at larger distances from the source for all cases that employed meteorological nudging, whereas the plume was situated somewhat more to the south in the

Figure 3.31: Vertical profiles of simulated areal mean wind direction (left), wind speed (middle), and potential temperature (right) for a domain approximately 50 km x 50 km around the Jaenschwalde power plant on 2018-05-23. Ribbons give temporal evolution over period of observations (09:00 to 10:45 UTC). Colors indicate different model configurations.

NONUDGE simulation. This is in agreement with the findings of mean wind directions in the previous section. Vertical column densities were in a similar range for all simulations. When looking at the time sequence of the plume there is a tendency of the TURB3 simulations to produce less horizontal dispersion than the other cases.

The same kind of model evaluation against observations as presented in detail for the CTRL case in Section 3.2 was carried out for all sensitivity runs and all different tracer release profiles. One aim of this analysis was, if possible, to deduce the most suitable model settings for the simulation of GHGs. Figures 3.33 and 3.34 present comparison statistics for the direct comparison to the observations and for a comparison that employed plume alignment on each flight transect. Results for each power plant were grouped into a single plot, possibly revealing the most suitable model configuration in each case.

There was large spread in the model performance statistics for both the direct and the aligned comparison. Generally alignment improved the results and reduced model RMSE below the standard deviation of the observations σ_{ref} in almost all cases. Similarly correlation coefficients improved largely by the alignment, whereas no impact on normalised standard deviation resulted. The performance statistics did not show any clear clustering of performance by model configuration. Clustering resulted mostly for individual flights and the three vertical release profiles, indicating that in these cases the model configuration had more impact than the release height. This was more true for the aligned comparison than for the direct comparison. Hence, the vertical release location mostly impacted the initial plume direction, for which the alignment corrected.

Despite the more complex structure of the plume for the Bełchatów case performance parameters were generally more favourable than for the Jaenschwalde case, a result that was already deduced from the CTRL case.

From the large scatter of model performance it is challenging to establish a most reliable model configuration. When taking individual performance parameters, the 'best' simulation with respect to individual observational flights can be established. Table 3.11 shows that no single configuration leads the comparison in all respects. For Bełchatów and the direct comparison, the NONUDGE configuration often yielded the best comparison results, which is surprising since the NONUDGE configuration showed least favourable results for the comparison of meteorological parameters. However, for the aligned comparison the NONUDGE case did not perform as well. For the calculated Taylor Skill Score and the aligned comparison the turbulence setting TURB3 often resulted in the highest scores. This is mainly due to normalised standard deviations close to 1 being estimated for this configuration. The larger standard deviations indicate that the plume in the case of TURB3 was less dispersive

Figure 3.32: Snapshot of the simulated total column CO₂ power plant plume of the Belchatów power station for different model configurations at 2018-06-07 13:00 UTC.

than for the other simulations. Nevertheless, other configurations performed better in terms of correlation coefficient and bias corrected RMSE, so the superiority of TURB3 cannot be generalised. The only model configuration that never appears in Table 3.11 is TURB1, potentially indicating that the employed switch by itself is not sufficient to improve turbulence representation.

In terms of best release height Table 3.11 again is not conclusive. Although for the CTRL case it was clear that BELC and JAEB best matched the observations, there is no such conclusion possible when looking at all sensitivity runs for Belchatów. For Jaenschwalde clearly JAEB led to the best model performance.

3.3.2.3 Ensemble variability

In order to further quantify the model uncertainty we analysed the ensemble variability of the simulated power plant plumes. As ensemble we took the 18 tracer simulations resulting from the six model configurations and three vertical tracer release profiles. For each output time the standard deviation of the simulated total column CO₂ relative to the ensemble mean was calculated. To avoid outliers, resulting values were only retained for grid cells with an ensemble mean larger than 1×10^{19} molec. cm⁻².

Figure 3.35 shows the spatial distribution of the relative ensemble standard deviation for two times for the Belchatów case and reduced to a resolution of 2 km x 2 km. Large values were mostly confined to shorter distances from the source and to the fringes of the plume. When arranging the results by distance from the source 3.36, a steady reduction of relative ensemble standard deviation is visible for distances larger 10 km. Reduced resolution resulted in larger median values but reduced extremes. The estimates beyond 35 km from the source should be regarded with care since they are only based on a few grid cells which fulfilled the minimal required mean vertical column density.

For Jaenschwalde relative ensemble standard deviation behaved very differently with distance to source. Values were slightly increasing with distance, especially at times when wind direction differed between the different sensitivity runs. Results differed little for other times of the same power plant.

Table 3.11: Best model configuration/release height with respect to correlation coefficient and Taylor Skill Score calculated from the direct comparison and using plume alignment along each flight transect.

Flight	Instrument	Direct		Aligned	
		Config	Release	Config	Release
<i>Correlation Coefficient</i>					
BEL DLR-Cessna	QCLS	CTRL	BELC	TURB3	BELB
BEL DLR-Halo	CRDS	NONUDGE	BELB	CTRL	BELB
BEL FUB-Cessna 1	MAMAP	NONUDGE	BELC	TURB134	BELA
BEL FUB-Cessna 2	MAMAP	NONUDGE	BELA	CTRL	BELC
BEL DLR-Halo	CHARM-F	CTRL	BELB	CTRL	BELB
JAE FUB-Cessna	CRDS	CTRL	JAEB	TURB4	JAEB
JAE FUB-Cessna	MAMAP	TURB134	JAEC	TURB4	JAEB
JAE DLR-Halo	CHARM-F	TURB134	JAEC	TURB4	JAEB
<i>Taylor Skill Score</i>					
BEL DLR-Cessna	QCLS	TURB3	BELC	TURB3	BELB
BEL DLR-Halo	CRDS	CTRL	BELC	CTRL	BELC
BEL FUB-Cessna 1	MAMAP	NONUDGE	BELC	CTRL	BELA
BEL FUB-Cessna 2	MAMAP	NONUDGE	BELA	TURB3	BELA
BEL DLR-Halo	CHARM-F	TURB3	BELA	TURB3	BELA
JAE FUB-Cessna	CRDS	TURB3	JAEB	TURB134	JAEB
JAE FUB-Cessna	MAMAP	TURB3	JAEB	TURB3	JAEB
JAE DLR-Halo	CHARM-F	TURB3	JAEB	TURB3	JAEB
<i>Bias corrected RMSE</i>					
BEL DLR-Cessna	QCLS	CTRL	BELB	CTRL	BELB
BEL DLR-Halo	CRDS	NONUDGE	BELB	CTRL	BELB
BEL FUB-Cessna 1	MAMAP	NONUDGE	BELC	TURB134	BELC
BEL FUB-Cessna 2	MAMAP	NONUDGE	BELA	NONUDGE	BELA
BEL DLR-Halo	CHARM-F	CTRL	BELB	CTRL	BELB
JAE FUB-Cessna	CRDS	CTRL	JAEB	TURB4	JAEB
JAE FUB-Cessna	MAMAP	TURB134	JAEC	TURB3	JAEB
JAE DLR-Halo	CHARM-F	TURB134	JAEB	TURB134	JAEB

Figure 3.33: Target (left) and Taylor (right) plot summarising performance statistics for all flight observations and model/tracer configurations for the Belchatów case. Upper panel: direct comparison; lower panel: comparison after adjustment for shift along flight transect. Different model configurations are displayed by different colors, while different symbols indicate different tracers released at different heights.

Figure 3.34: Target (left) and Taylor (right) plot summarising performance statistics for all flight observations and model/tracer configurations for the Jaenschwalde case. Upper panel: direct comparison; lower panel: comparison after adjustment for shift along each flight transect. Different model configurations are displayed by different colors, while different symbols indicate different tracers released at different heights.

Figure 3.35: Spatial distribution of relative ensemble standard deviation of CO₂ vertical column density of the Bełchatów power plant plume, calculated from 18 tracer simulations and given for two times: 2018-06-07 11:00 UTC and 13:00 UTC. Spatial resolution was reduced to 2 km x 2 km.

Figure 3.36: Boxplot of relative ensemble standard deviation of CO₂ vertical column density of the Bełchatów power plant plume as function of distance from source, calculated from 18 tracer simulations and given for two times: 2018-06-07 11:00 UTC and 13:00 UTC. Results presented for original horizontal resolution (1 km x 1 km) and reduced resolution at 2 km x 2 km.

Figure 3.37: Boxplot of relative ensemble standard deviation of CO₂ vertical column density of the Jaenschwalde power plant plume as function of distance from source, calculated from 18 tracer simulations and given for two times: 2018-05-23 07:00 UTC and 09:30 UTC. Results presented for original horizontal resolution (1 km x 1 km) and reduced resolution at 2 km x 2 km.

3.4 Impact of model transport uncertainty on emission estimation

Emissions may be estimated from satellite observations of CO₂ plumes in several different ways. A satellite like OCO-2 (or a possible future Lidar mission) measures total columns along a narrow transect through the plume. CO2M, conversely, will be able to image the whole extent of the plume in a single overpass. Emissions can then be quantified by assimilating the observations into an atmospheric transport model or by applying a mass-balance approach Kuhlmann et al. (2020a). Uncertainties in the quantification may arise from uncertainties in the measurements and in the transport model used in an inversion, or from uncertainties in the estimated wind speed and background concentrations in a mass-balance approach. An additional source of uncertainty may be flow situations with turbulent elements sufficiently large to be resolved by the satellite. In such a case, estimates derived from single transects (OCO-2) or single snapshots of the whole plume (CO2M) can be biased even in case of perfect measurements and perfect knowledge of the flow field.

In this section, we first analyze how turbulence puts a fundamental limit to the ability to quantify emissions from individual vertical cross-sections through the plume. Second, we apply the analytical inversion and the mass balance method described in Kuhlmann et al. (2020a) to the simulated total column XCO₂ fields mimicking the situation with real satellite observations. Results from both methods are compared to the 'true' emissions as used in the transport model.

3.4.1 Methods

3.4.1.1 Flux estimate from three-dimensional model data

Figure 3.38: Example of location of vertical slices through the Bełchatów power plant plume at 2018-06-07 9:00 UTC (left). Model mole fractions given for vertical level with maximal emissions. Vertical cross section (right) of power plant plume at 5th cross section (10 km from the source). Isolines give the wind speed perpendicular to the vertical cross section, with dashed isolines for negative values.

To deduce the point source emissions, a simple approach employing the complete three-dimensional model data was applied. The approach is based on the assumption that the horizontal mass flux through a vertical cross section of the emerging plume is equal to the emission flux. However, this is not necessarily true when applied to snapshots of 'mean' model data, since the flux will fluctuate in the presence of grid-resolved turbulent motions. It will not even be true when averaging over long time periods (i.e., over many turbulent eddies), since it is neglecting the mass flux by subgrid-scale turbulence, although it can generally be assumed that its contribution in downwind direction is small. It is thus worth analysing how uncertain the estimate becomes when applied to individual transects and snapshots of the plume in a flow with kilometer-scale turbulent elements as simulated for the Belchatow case.

For each model output step, a series of 20 vertical cross sections were taken from the model data at distances from 2 to 40 km. The cross sections were aligned perpendicular to the plume direction by defining the latter by the average simulated wind direction at the vertical level with maximum emissions. The width and depth of the cross section was chosen sufficiently large to accommodate the plume at all times. An example of the positioning of the cross sections is given in Figure 3.38.

For each cross section, the total tracer flux was calculated by extracting the wind speed perpendicular to the cross section and multiplying it by the simulated tracer mass at the cross section and final integration over the whole cross section. Figure 3.38 shows the tracer mole fraction at an example cross section together with the wind speed. The example illustrates a rather well defined case with a compact plume centered around 1200 m a.s.l. embedded in a fairly homogeneous wind field. Nevertheless, the strong wind gradient towards the top of the atmospheric boundary layer, the counter flow above and the emerging wind variability on the sides of the plume illustrate that even for this well defined plume, the source of uncertainty will be spatio-temporal variability in the involved variables.

3.4.1.2 Flux estimate from two-dimensional model data

An approach more relevant for the application to satellite observations estimates emissions from two-dimensional total column XCO₂ fields. For this purpose, we created a time series of synthetic CO₂M XCO₂ observations for each point source using the control case. We cut out a 250 km × 250 km square that includes the complete plume from the XCO₂ model fields and spatially binned the fields to create pixels of 2.2 by 2.2 km. To account for measurement uncertainty, we added random noise of 0.5 ppm to the satellite image.

For Bełchatów, we used 15-minute model output from 10:00 to 16:00 UTC to create 25 synthetic images. For Jänschwalde, we created 17 images using model output from 07:00 to 11:00 UTC. Figure 3.39 shows examples of the synthetic XCO₂ observations.

Figure 3.39: Time series of synthetic CO₂ satellite images of emission plumes for (a) Bełchatów and (b) Jänschwalde.

Emissions were then estimated using the approaches presented in Kuhlmann et al. (2020a) and applied in Work Package 1, i.e. (a) an analytical inversion and (b) a data-driven mass-balance approach. The analytical inversion fits a simulated plume signature and CO₂ background field to the synthetic observations using a least squares fit. Different from Work Package 1, however, where the inversion was based on the same simulation that was used to create the synthetic observations, the plume signature and background field were taken not only from the control run but also from other model realisations with different model settings and release heights. This allows investigating the impact of transport model uncertainties on the inversion results.

The mass-balance approach detects the location of the plume using the algorithm described in Section 2.3 and the quantification method described in Section 2.5. Since NO₂ fields were not included in the model study, NO₂ observations are neither used for plume detection nor for supporting the computation of line densities.

3.4.2 Results

3.4.2.1 Flux estimate from three-dimensional model data

Figure 3.40: Time series of mass fluxes through different cross sections of the Belchatów power plant plume on 2018-06-07 (left). Individual colored lines refer to estimates through different cross sections, whereas dots and error bars give the mean and standard deviation of the individual estimates. The black dotted line gives the power plant emissions as used in the model. Colored boxes on the right give the temporal mean and standard deviation for each cross section with the gray bar in the background providing the power plant emissions.

In the case of the Belchatów power plant plume, which was sampled and analysed during a very turbulent and convective period, the mass flux as calculated for individual cross sections through the model data was very variable in time and from transect to transect 3.40. In the afternoon, the range between minimum and maximum flux at a given time could be as large as a factor of three, suggesting that a satellite like OCO-2 could determine the emissions for such a turbulent plume only with a large uncertainty even in the case of perfect measurements and perfect knowledge of the wind field and plume structure. The average flux computed over all cross sections, which would be more comparable to the situation of a CO₂M satellite imaging the whole plume, was much closer to the 'true' emission flux, but varied over time with periods of significant deviations from the 'truth' of the order of 20%. The temporal mean fluxes through individual cross sections agreed well with the 'true' emission flux, with the tendency of overestimating it at short distances from the source and underestimating it for farther cross sections. The reason for the latter could be that some scenes showed a return flux above the boundary layer that would act to lower the flux estimate in the current approach.

When looking at the ensemble of the mean fluxes over all cross sections as taken from different model sensitivity runs 3.41, it is interesting to note that for most of the ensemble members the flux estimate for the Belchatów case followed the same temporal variability. Furthermore, the ensemble spread got larger during the afternoon hours when the flow was most turbulent. Nevertheless, the average ensemble mean bias when compared with the 'true' flux was relatively small (2.8%) and average standard deviations were in the order of 13%. There was a general tendency of flux estimates being lower for lower model release heights. Currently, no plausible explanation for this behaviour can be given.

For the Jaenschwalde power plant plume, which was simulated under less turbulent conditions, variability of the flux estimates was smaller between the different ensemble members and also over time. Again, systematically larger emission estimates were connected with the highest tracer release height before 9:00 UTC. Afterwards there was no such distinction. Despite smaller variability (standard deviation of 10%), a larger overall bias (-7%) than for the Belchatów case was estimated. The larger bias may be a result of the more compact plume structure in combination with limited model resolution, which may offset the above flux calculation from the 'true' flux in the model itself. Another possibility could be the neglect of any subgrid-scale turbulent flux

Figure 3.41: Time series of CO₂ flux estimate taken as average over all cross sections and given for all six COSMO-GHG sensitivity runs and three release profiles (CO2_A, CO2_B, CO2_C) of the Bełchatów power plant. Model emissions are given by the dashed black line. The overall bias and standard deviation over the whole period is given in the lower right corner.

Figure 3.42: Time series of CO₂ flux estimate taken as average over all cross sections and given for all six COSMO-GHG sensitivity runs and three release profiles (CO2_A, CO2_B, CO2_C) of the Jaenschwalde power plant. Model emissions are given by the dashed black line. The overall bias and standard deviation over the whole period is given in the lower right corner.

through the cross sections. However, wind speeds were larger in the Jaenschwalde case, which should result in an even smaller contribution of horizontal turbulent fluxes when compared to the flux by the mean flow.

3.4.2.2 Flux estimate from two-dimensional model data

Figure 3.43 shows the estimated CO₂ emissions of Bełchatów and Jänschwalde using the analytical inversion and the mass-balance approach. The analytical inversion agrees well with the true emissions for the perfect transport model (control run) but strongly underestimates the emissions for all other simulations with different turbulence settings or vertical release heights. The reason for this underestimation is that simulated and "observed" (real) plume do not fully overlap, so that parts of the simulated plume are compared to actual background values in the least squares minimization process. The degree of underestimation correlates with the degree of spatial mismatch, which illustrates the problem that a simple inversion, not accounting for differences in plume structure and direction, may lead to significantly biased estimates. The mean bias is -24.3% and -20.3% for Bełchatów and Jänschwalde, and the standard deviation considering all estimates is 13.9% and 24.6%, respectively. One approach to address this issue could be to increase the uncertainty for pixels near the edges of the plume where differences between individual simulations were the largest (see Fig. 3.24), but this would likely only reduce but not eliminate the biases.

Figure 3.43: Time series of CO₂ emissions of different satellite images of the (left) Bełchatów and (right) Jänschwalde power plant using the (upper) analytical inversion and (lower) mass-balance approach. The black line shows the true emissions. The markers with black edges are estimates using the same model fields as for generating the synthetic satellite observations. The different lines show the estimates for different model settings and release heights.

The time series of the CO₂ emissions estimated with the mass-balance approach look quite different. The estimates for the different release heights and model settings show a surprisingly small spread for Bełchatow and a somewhat larger spread for Jaenschwalde, where the results indicate a clustering by vertical release height. The results appear to be dominated by the assumption of mean wind speed of the plume (taken from the wind speed at the source location), rather than by the different turbulent structures of the plumes. The standard deviations are similar as for the analytical inversion with 15.0% and 29.0% for Bełchatów and Jänschwalde, respectively.

For Bełchatów, CO₂ emissions are underestimated (mean bias: -29.1%) likely because the plume detection algorithm fails to detect the full extent of the turbulent plume. As a result, the background field would be

over- and the plume signal underestimated. Another reason could be that the wind speeds at the source are on average lower than those in the plume. For Jänschwalde, the mean bias is only 5.4% likely because the plume was less turbulent and spatially more constrained, which leads to a more concentrated plume that can be more easily detected over its full extent. However, the temporal and ensemble variability was twice as large in this case, possibly because the plume was quite narrow and quickly dispersing, resulting only in a small number of detected plume pixels. Since no NO₂ plume detection was done here, the case is a good example for an emission estimation that would most likely benefit from additional plume pixels being identified.

The exercise shows that an analytical inversion will fail when transport errors due to different model settings and plume release heights are not considered in the inversion framework. In this case, the resulting uncertainties have similar magnitude as the data-driven mass-balance approach. The uncertainties in the mass-balance approach do not have the same origin as the uncertainties in the inversion. This results in the interesting possibility to combine the strengths of both methods in order to improve the estimation of CO₂ emissions beyond what is possible with only one approach.

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